

Online forum materiallari to'plami

25-fevral 2023-yil

Muhammad ibn Muso al-Xorazmiy tavalludining
1240 yilligiga bag'ishlangan

"Yosh olimlar, doktorant va tadqiqotchilarning onlayn ilmiy
forumi"

Muhammad ibn Muso al-Xorazmiy nomidagi
Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
Farg'ona filiali

Farg'ona - 2023

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5-sho'ba materiallari to'plami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7750449>

To'plamga 2023 yil 25 fevral kuni

Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universitetida "Engineering problems and innovations" jurnali tahririyati bilan hamkorlikda o'tkazilgan "Muxandislik muammolari va innovatsiyalar" mavzusidagi yosh olimlar, doktorantlar va tadqiqotchilarning onlayn ilmiy forumi 5-sho'ba ishtirokchilarining ilmiy ma'ruza materiallari kiritilgan

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ABU ALI IBN SINO VA ABU NASR FAROBIYNING ILMIIY-FALSAFIY MEROSINI O'RGANISH

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TATU Farg'ona filiali dotsenti, falsafa fanlari bo'yicha PhD

***Annotatsiya.** Maqolada Uyg'onish davrining buyuk mutafakkirlari Abu Ali ibn Sino va Abu Nasr Farobiyning ilmiy merosi o'rganilib, ular tomonidan qoldirilgan boy ma'naviy merosimiz durdonalari bo'lgan falsafiy asarlari taxlil qilingan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Ibn Sino, Farobiy, falsafiy qissalar, fozil odamlar, nafs, jon, ruxiyat, meros, tasavvuf.*

Mamlakatimizda ilm-fanning fundamental yo'nalishlari bo'yicha yirik kashfiyotlarni amalga oshirgan buyuk mutafakkirlarimizdan Abu Ali ibn Sino va Abu Nasr Farobiyning ilmiy merosi, jamiyat taraqqiyotining yangi bosqichida talabalar axloqiy madaniyatini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan ilmiy manbalardan hisoblanadi. O'zbekistonda yoshlarda axloqiy madaniyatni shakllantirish, xususan ilmiy bilishga bo'lgan qiziqishini kuchaytirishda dunyo ilm-fani va madaniyati rivojiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan olimlarimizning ilmiy merosidan foydalanish orqali «jahon tsivilizatsiyasiga bebaho hissa qo'shgan ajdodlarimizning boy madaniy merosini chuqur o'rganish asosida yoshlarning ongu tafakkurini shakllantirish» mamlakatimizda ustuvor vazifa hisoblanadi¹.

Ta'kidlash lozimki mamlakat rahbarining “Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi” asarida ham mutafakkirlar ilmiy merosining kadrlar tayyorlashdagi ahamiyati qayd etilgan. “Ajdodlarimizning armonlari o'sha davrda Imom Buxoriy, Imom Termiziy, Muhammad Xorazmiy, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Ahmad Farg'oniy, Abu Mansur Moturidiy, Abu Hamid Usturlobiy, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sino kabi mutafakkir bobolarimiz xayoti va faoliyati, asarlarida o'z talqinini topgan adolat va adolatparvarlik g'oyalarida mujassam bo'ldi”².

Ibn Sino “Salomon va Ibsol” falsafiy qissasini yozishida bevosita emas, bilvosita bo'lsa ham Abu Nasr Farobiyning eng mashhur falsafiy asari “Arou ahli madinatul – fozila” (“Fozillar shahri aholisining hayotiy qarashlari”, qisqasi – “Fozil odamlar shahri”) asaridan ijodiy ta'sirlangani sezilib turadi. Abu Nasr Farobiy asarida “Fozillar shahri” deb shartli atalgan ideal shaharni adolatli boshqarish tamoyillarini belgilashda Aflotunning “Davlat va Qonunlar” asarlarida ko'tarilgan masalalarga ham munosabat bildirib ketadi. Lekin Abu Nasr Farobiy asarining Aflotun asarlaridan jiddiy farqlanishi ham yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi.

Abu Nasr Farobiy tabiiy ravishda musulmon dunyosi faylasufi sifatida Platon asaridagi mushriklik, ko'p – xudolilikni, boshqacha aytganda majusiylikni inkor etadi. Buning o'rniga Abu Nasr Farobiy “Fozil odamlar shahri” asarining boshlang'ich qismidagi boblarida monotsizm – yakka xudolilikdan – tavhidning asosiy tamoyillarini, teran falsafiy mohiyatini ochib beradi. Bu asarning 33-bobida fozillar shahri aholisining umumiy xususiyatlari haqida fikr yuritiladi. Fozillar shahri aholisi uchun umumiy xususiyatlar quyidagilardir:

Birinchidan, ular asliy sababni (olam va undagi mavjudotlar nima uchun yaratilganini) va Asliy sabab (Tangri taolo) ning barcha sifatlarini bilish zarur. (Tangrining barcha sifatleri iymoni mufassal kalimasida aniq aytilgan: Alloh yakkadir, uning sherigi yo'qdir, u – doimo tirik, mangu o'lmaydi. U barcha mavjudotlarga hayot beruvchidir, u barcha narsaga qodir, qudrat sohibidir.)

Ikkinchidan, ular moddiylikdan tashqari narsalarni (aqliy bilimlarni, farishtalarni, ruhiy

¹ Диний-маърифий соҳа фаолиятини тубдан такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 16.04.2018 йилдаги ПФ-5416 Фармони. Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 18.04.2018 й., 06/18/5416/1079-сон, 13.12.2018 й., 06/18/5597/2300-сон.

² Шавкат Мирзиёев. Янги Ўзбекистон тараққиёт стратегияси. Тошкент. “Ўзбекистон” 2022 й. 16 - бет

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olam hodisalarini) va ularning sifatlarini, mavjudotlarning faol aqlgacha bo'lgan darajalarini hamda ulardan har birining sifatlarini;

Uchinchidan, fozil odamlar saloviy xilqatlarni (sayyoralarni, to'qqiz osmon va ulardagi yulduzlarni) va ulardan (osmonlardan) har birining sifatlarini bilishi zarur.

To'rinchidan, so'ng shu (samoviy) xilqatlardan pastdagi jismlarni, ularning qanday vujudga kelishi va yo'qolishini (shu haqda Ibn Sino "Kavn va Fasod" nomli asar yozgan) hamda ularda yuz berayotgan barcha hodisalarning (tabiat hodisalarining) mukammalligi yaxlitligi, muruvvat, adolat bilan (yaratilgani), oqilona ekanligini.

Beshinchidan, fozil odamlar yana odamzod qanday yaralganini, (uning jismiga kirgan) ruhning xususiyatlarini, faol aql uning ruhini qanday nurlantirganini, shu tufayli insonda dastlabki tushunchalar paydo bo'lganligini, u (odamzod) nimalarda Allohning irodasiga bo'ysunishi, nimalarda erkinligini;

Oltinchidan, Fozil odamlar, ya'ni shahar (davlat) ning birinchi rahbari biror yoqqa ketganida yoki kasalligida uning o'rnini bosa oladigan rahbarlarni;

Ettinchidan, Fozillar shahri aholisi yana dillari erishadigan baxt – saodat nima ekanligini;

Sakkizinchidan, ular yana fazilatsiz shaharlar aholisi o'lganidan so'ng ruhlari oxiratda ne kechishini, ba'zilar baxtsizlikka, falokatga uchrab (azob chekishini), ba'zilar yo'q bo'lib ketishini;

To'qqizinchidan, fozillar shahri aholisi oxiratda nelarga erishuvini, nimalardan (qanday jazolardan) saqlanishini bilishlari zarur.

Abu Nasr Forobiy jaholatdagi va adashgan shaharlar ahllarining bir qancha turlarini ko'rsatadi. Bular:

1. Ayirboshlovchilar shahri.
2. Razolat va badbaxtlik shahri.
3. Obro'parastlar shahri.
4. Amalparastlar va hokimiyatparastlar shahri.
5. SHahvatparastlar shahri va boshqalar.

Alloma Abu Nasr Forobiy shahvatparastlar shahri haqida bunday deydi: "Bunday shahar aholisining har biri ehtiroslari tizginini jilovlamay, istalgancha shahvat nafslarini, tuban mayllarini qondirishga intiladi."³

Ibn Sino ontologiyasi va gnoseologiyasida, ya'ni borliq va uni bilish haqidagi falsafiy ta'limotida, inson jismi va nafs (jon, ruh) munosabatlari haqidagi ilmiy qarashlar asosiy o'rinni egallaydi. Jumladan, mutafakkir qalamiga mansub bo'lgan "Ash-SHifo" asarining mavzulari serqirra bo'lib, eng muhim qismi nafs va ruhiyat (psixika) haqidagi ta'limotni tashkil etadi. Ibn Sinoning nafs (jon va ruh) haqidagi asosiy g'oyalari hozirgi vaqtgacha ilmiy haqiqat asoslangan falsafiy xulosa sifatida o'zining nazariy, metodologik ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. Uning ruhiyatga doir ilmiy qarashlari tibbiyot-meditsinaga doir xulosalari bilan uzviy bog'liqdir. O'tmishdagi ko'pchilik donishmandlar va xususan Aristotel kabi, Ibn Sino ham ruhni nomoddiy, ya'ni ma'naviyat hodisasi deb biladi. Hozirgi zamon falsafa fanida vitalizm (vita-jon, hayot) oqimi tarafdorlari ham vujudning hayotini ruh boshqaradi deb hisoblaydilar.⁴

Ibn Sinoning asosiy falsafiy merosi "Ash-SHifo", "An-Najot", "Al-Ishorot va-at-tanbeh" asarlarida nafs, jon, ruh mohiyati, ruhning vujudga ta'siri, jism va ruhning o'zaro munosabatlari asosiy masalalar sifatida tahlil va tadqiq etiladi. Ibn Sino avvalo, bu masalalar haqida o'tmishdagi donishmandlar aytgan fikrlarni chuqur ko'rib chiqadi. Donishmand Aristotel ham "Ruh haqida" asarining boshlanishida o'zidan avvalgi qadimgi yunon faylasuflari Fales, Demokrit, Geraklit, Anaksimandr va boshqalarning shu haqidagi qarashlarini keltirib, ularga munosabat bildirgan. U (Aristotel) "Jon haqida" asarining 2-bobida Levkipp, Demokrit va

³ Abu Nasr Farobiy. Fozil odamlar sha'ri. – Toshkent: Xalq merosi, 1993. – C.149.

⁴ Abu Nasr Farobiy, Fozil odamlar sha'ri. – Toshkent: Xalq merosi, 1993. – C. 149.

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Pifagorchilarning jon va ruh haqidagi qarashlarini bayon qiladi.

Yunon faylasufi, mutafakkir Demokrit fikricha, jon to'rt unsur - asoslardan biri olovdur va u issiqdir. Olov bilan jon quyosh nurida havo zarralarining harakati ko'rinishiga o'xshaydi. Hyp bo'lmasa havo zarralari harakati ko'rinmaydi.

Ibn Sino ham "Nafs (Jon) haqida" asarida xuddi shu misolni – quyosh nurida havo zarralarining harakati ko'rinishini aytadi. Ibn Sino Aristotelning "Jon haqida" asarini yoki Abu Nasr Forobiy va al-Kindiyning falsafiy sharhini o'qigan bo'lishi mumkin. Mutafakkirlar Demokrit, Levkip ham jonni moddiy deb, u Quyosh nurida ko'ringan havo zarralariday sharsimon mayda zarralar-atomlardan iboratdir deb biladilar. Ularning fikricha, havodan nafas olganida jon bor, ya'ni badan tirikdir, nafas olinmasa, u o'likka aylanadi. Bu ikkala mutafakkir (Demokrit va Levkip) jonni, atomlarni o'z-o'zini harakatlantiruvchi quvvatga ega deb hisoblaydilar. Jismda hayot yo'qolganida esa, nafas olinmagani uchun, bu harakat ham to'xtaydi. Mutafakkirning yozishicha, pifagorchilar ham jon haqida shunga o'xshash fikrlaydilar, ya'ni jon - havo zarralari - atomlarning harakatidan iborat. Aristotel bularning fikrlarini nozik madaniyat, hurmat bilan tanqid qiladi. Bu mutafakkirlar o'ylaydiki, jon boshqa narsalarni harakatga keltiradi, o'zi esa o'zicha harakatlanadi. Bu donishmandlar jonni harakatga keltirgan zotni (ya'ni, Xudoni) ko'rmaydilar.⁵

Ibn Sino «Al-Ishorat va-at-Tanbeh» asarida bunday yozadi: «Biz aytamiz: o'tmishdoshlarimizning bu masala haqidagi fikrlarida ixtilof bor, ya'ni bir-biriga o'xshamaydi. Ularning ba'zilar nafsni jon harakati deb, boshqalari idrok vositasi deb, uchinchilar shu ikkala fikrni to'g'ri deb, to'rtinchilar hayot yo'li, turli qismlarga bo'linmaydi, deb talqin qilganlar. Nafs jonning harakati deb o'ylovchilar jismni birinchi harakatlantiruvchi quvvat - ruh deb hisoblaydilar. Ular fikricha, harakat ruhdan asab tolalariga, tanadagi turli a'zolarga, muskullarga o'tadi. Ular ruhni o'z-o'zidan harakatlanuvchi quvvat deb bilganlar. O'z-o'zidan harakatlanuvchi quvvat esa hech qachon butunlay, tamomila yo'qolishi mumkin emas.

Ular aytadilarki, samoviy jismlar yo'qolmaydilar, chunki ular o'zicha doimiy harakatdadirlar. Ba'zilar (Aristotel har bir donishmandning ismini aytadi: Fales, Ksenofan, Empedokl, Anaksagor...) aytadilarki, ruh moddiy jism emas, u o'zicha harakatlanuvchi va moddasiz javhar (substantsiya)dir. Ba'zi tadqiqotchilar fikriga ko'ra aksincha, ruh o'zicha harakatlanuvchi jismdir, deydilar. Ba'zi faylasuflar ta'kidlashicha, nafs (jon) bo'linmaydigan, sharsimon modda bo'lib, sharligi sababli doimiy harakati osonlashadi. Ular nafas olishni jon uchun ozuqa deydilar, chunki nafas jonni saqlaydi, nafas quyosh nuri tutamida ko'rinadigan chang zarralariga o'xshash bo'linmas moddalarni harakatga keltiradi. SHuningdek bir guruh izlanuvchilar aytadilarki, bu bo'linmas tanachalar jon emas, jon ularni harakatga keltiradi. Yana ba'zilar o'ylashicha, jon (nafas) olovdur va u doimo harakatdadir.⁶

Ibn Sinoning nafs (jon) haqidagi qarashlari yunon faylasuflari, Demokrit va Levkipga emas, balki mutafakkir Arastu qarashlariga yaqindir. Ibn Sino ruhni abadiy, yo'qolmas mohiyat sifatida ifodalaydi. Allomaning fikricha, inson ruhi iymon-e'tiqodni kashf etishga qobiliyatlidir. Allohning tajalliysi bo'lgan, avvalgi Aql bilan inson ruhi o'zaro aloqadadir. Ibn Sinoning ruh haqidagi qarashlari islomiy shariatga zid hisoblanar edi. SHu sababli atoqli ilohiyotchi, teosof (diniy faylasuf) Abu Hamid G'azzoliy "Tahofut-ul-falosifa" ("Faylasuflarga raddiya") asarida Abu Nasr Forobiy va Ibn Sinoni xayulo (materiya) yo'qdan bor bo'lmaydi, deganlari uchun tanqid qilgan edi. Ibn Sino fikricha, nafs (jon) moddiy emas. Inson ruhi ma'naviy vujud va u sonanoqsiz quvvatlarga va imkoniyatlarga egadir. Ayi vaqtda unda soddalik ham bor.

Ibn Sinoning ta'kidlashicha, insoniyatga ruh aqliy quvvatga egadir. Odam ruhi turli maqsadlarni amalga oshirish uchun aqliy quvvatini muntazam ishga soladi. Insonning bu quvvati aslida ruhnik bo'lib, ruh va aql o'rtasidagi uzviy munosabat sabab va oqibat o'rtasidagi

⁵ Аристотель. О душе. Сочинения. Том I. – Москва: Мысль, 1966. – С. 369-450.

⁶ Абу Али ибн Сина. Избранные философские произведения. – Москва: Наука, 1980. – С. 28.

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munosabat sifatida ham kasb etadi. Ruh (agar turli-tuman istak, mayllar bilan ifloslanmagan, toza bo'lsa) ziddiyat va qarama-qarshiliklardan holdir va shu sababli u yo'qolmaydi.

Inson ruhi va vujudi aloqasi oldinma keyinlik munosabatida emas. Ruh vujud vositasida harakat qiladi va tanada jon yo'qolganida ruh o'z vazifasini bajarib bo'ladi. Tananing buzilishi (fasodi) va yo'qolishi ruhning buzilishiga va yo'qolishiga olib kelmaydi. SHu munosabat bilan alloma ta'kidlaydiki, Pyh sababli inson paydo bo'ladi. Tanaga ruhning kirishi bilan u tananing ruhiga aylanadi. Ruh tana uchun hayotiy ma'naviy, ruhoniyl quvvatlarni tashkil etadi. SHu sababli, ruh ma'naviyat hodisasidir. Inson tug'ilgan kunlaridan boshlab, o'z ruhini ko'rsata boshlaydi. Ibn Sino shu masalada juda ko'p yechilmagan, kashf qilinmagan sirlar borligini aytadi. Alloma ta'kidlashicha, ruh o'z holicha badanga itoat qilmaydi. Azaliyl ruh musaffodir, shu sababli u azaliyl joyiga, musaffolikka qaytishga intiladi. SHu ma'noda ruhning inson badaniga kirishi Platon aytgan mifologik hikoyalardagi kabi xatolik sababli emasdir. Ruh o'zini kamol toptirish uchun badanga, vujudga ehtiyoji bor. U badan vositasida oliyl mukammallikka erishadi⁷.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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⁷ Абу Наср Фаробий. Фозил одамлар шаҳри. – Тошкент: Халқ мероси, 1993. – С. 149.

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МЕТОД ФИЛЬТРАЦИИ СПАМА НА ОСНОВЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОЙ НЕЙРОННОЙ СЕТИ**Набижонов Равшанбек Мухаммаджон ўгли***Ассистент кафедры информационных технологий ТУИТ Ферганского филиала***Мансуров Абдусид Вохиджон ўгли***ТУИТ Ферганского филиала Студент 618-21 группы*

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается задача фильтрации спама и наиболее распространенные подходы к ее решению: на основе списков адресов, сигнатур, теоремы Байеса в сравнении с методами искусственного интеллекта. Задача фильтрации спама является актуальной проблемой, так как технологии создания спама развиваются следом за средствами защиты от спама, что требует переосмысления подходов к задаче фильтрации спама и применения методов и средств искусственного интеллекта.

Ключевые слова: фильтрация спама; искусственные нейронные сети; искусственный интеллект; спам; классификация сообщений; выделение признаков сообщений; перцептрон; информационная безопасность.

В современном мире, где реклама является двигателем торговли, с развитием сети Internet и средств общения, проблема нежелательной рекламы [6] и сообщений требует интеллектуального подхода для ее решения. Современные методы борьбы со спамом, основанные на лингвистических сигнатурах, правилах фильтрации сообщений, становятся все менее эффективными [6, 8], так как требуется увеличение трудозатрат специалистов по защите от спама на поддержание этих сигнатур и правил в актуальном состоянии. Таким образом, современные методы борьбы со спамом требуют постоянного участия человека для эффективного анализа текста, они не способны самостоятельно вырабатывать эти правила, то есть самообучаться. Если рассматривать человека как средство борьбы со спамом, то можно сказать, что он обладает способностью обнаружения признаков спама, основываясь на собственном опыте и предпочтениях, знаниях о добровольных новостных и рекламных подписках, обучаемостью, его работа не сводится к шаблонам и потому более эффективна. Именно поэтому задача создания средства борьбы со спамом сводится к наделению средства борьбы со спамом навыками и качествами, присущими человеку: способность к обучению, система предпочтений и исключений, анализ контекста, система принятия решений [6, 7, 8].

Предлагаемый автором статьи метод фильтрации спама основан на использовании нейронной сети, выступающей в качестве механизма принятия решений, давая на выходе вероятностную оценку «спамности» всего сообщения. Искусственная нейронная сеть обладает способностью обучаться (в том числе, обобщать свои знания, накапливать опыт), является наиболее приближенной моделью человеческого мозга, как по архитектуре, так и по принципам работы. Более подробно читатель может ознакомиться с свойствами искусственной нейронной сети и моделированию человеческой деятельности и мышления в [1, 2, 3, 4].

Задача обеспечения информационной безопасности, куда входит и защита от спама, является нетривиальным ресурсоемким процессом. Для увеличения эффективности и повышения степени автоматизированности процесса защиты информации с целью освобождения человеческих ресурсов наиболее перспективным направлением является внедрение нейросетевых технологий в существующие системы защиты. Так, например, нейронные сети получили широкое распространение в системах обнаружения и отражения сетевых атак. В таких системах, как и в предлагаемом автором статьи методе, нейронные сети анализируют комплекс разнородных параметров сети (время ответа сервера, Набижонов Р.М. & Мансуров А.В. (2023). Yosh olimlar, doktorantlar va tadqiqotchilarning onlayn ilmiy forumi. *Метод фильтрации спама на основе искусственной нейронной сети*, 7-9. TATUFF-EPAI.

отклонение пакетов от стандартов RFC и прочее), выявляя аномальное поведение и способны опознавать даже те атак, которых не было в обучающей выборке благодаря способности нейронных сетей к обобщению и обучению. Предлагаемая автором статьи система фильтрации спама принципиально схожа с подобными системами обнаружения и отражения атак, только обнаруживаются не сетевые атаки, а сообщения, чье содержание является нежелательной рекламой (спамом). Отличие состоит в том, что предлагаемая система фильтрации спама работает на уровне приложения, согласно модели OSI, а не на уровне сети, как системы обнаружения атак, и анализируются не флаги пакетов, а непосредственно данные, т.е. содержание сообщений.

Рисунок 1.

Любая нейронная сеть имеет входы, выходы, собственно нейроны и связи между ними (синапсы, аксоны, дендриты) [4]. Схема простой нейронной сети изображена на рисунке 1.

Схема нейронной сети.

1 - нейроны входного слоя;

2 - нейроны скрытого слоя;

3 - нейрон выходного слоя

На примере человека рассмотрим процесс обнаружения спама в сообщении. Во-первых, существует ряд слов и словосочетаний, которые довольно часто встречаются в спаме (например, «buy something with 50% discount»). Однако, это не является достаточным основанием для отнесения такого сообщения к спаму. В этом случае человек дополнительно обращает внимание на контекст и смысл сообщения, его общую направленность, также он может обратить внимание на орфографические, синтаксические и морфологические особенности текста. Исходя из этой совокупности, с гораздо большей достоверностью можно принять решение о том, является ли данное сообщение спамом или нет.

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JAMIYAT RIVOJIDA FAN VA TEXNOLOGIYA O'RNI**To'xtasinov Azamat G'ofurovich***Farg'ona politexnika instituti, Intellektual muhandislik tizimlari kafedrasida o'qituvchisi*

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada jamiyat taraqqiyotining muhim yo'lishlarini tez suratlarda rivojlanishining asosiy omil bu ilmiy bilimlarning to'planishi va fundamental tadqiqotlardan olingan natija jamiyat hayotiga to'g'ri yo'naltirilganligi haqidagi ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: fundamental tadqiqotlar, elektrotexnika, internet, axborot-kommunikatsiya, foton nazariyasi, transistor.

Ilmiy va texnologik faoliyat deganda noma'lum hodisalarni yoritish, yangi tabiiy qonunlar va tamoyillarni kashf qilish orqali yangi bilimlarni yaratish tushuniladi va olingan yangi bilimlar keyinchalik jamiyat rivojlanishida qo'llaniladi. Fan va texnologiyaning jamiyatga qanday hissa qo'shishining mohiyati yangi bilimlarni yaratish, so'ngra bu bilimlarni inson hayotining farovonligini oshirish va jamiyat oldida turgan turli muammolarni hal qilish uchun ishlatiladi. Ilmiy bilimlarning to'planishi va fundamental tadqiqotlar natijasida olingan xulosalarni taqqoslash orqali fanning o'ziga xos qiymati o'trib borishini ko'rish mumkin. Ilmiy bilimlar asosida turli xil yangi texnologik tadqiqot va ishlanmalarning xilma-xilligi bilan taqqoslash mumkin. Jamiyat va hayotining farovonligini oshiradigan amaliy texnologiyalarni yaratadigan tadqiqot va ishlanmalarga, jamiyat oldida turgan turli muammolarga javob berish uchun fan va texnologiyadan foydalanishga ehtiyoj tug'iladi. Jamiyat taraqqiyotini fan va texnika vositasida amalga oshirish ilmiy bilimlarni yetarli darajada to'plashni taqozo etadi. Texnologiya inson hayotining qulayligi va farovonligi bilan chambarchas bog'liq holda rivojlangan bo'lsa, tabiiy fan falsafadan kelib chiqqan va odamlarning intellektual qiziqishi bilan qo'llab-quvvatlangan. Texnologik taraqqiyot turli ilm-fan yutuqlari bilan ta'minlangan bo'lsada, bu ilmiy tadqiqotlar yangi texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish maqsadida olib borilgan degani emas, balki ilmiy bilimlardan faqat mavjud bo'lganligi sababli foydalanilgan.

Sanoat inqilobidan keyin fan va texnikaning alohida yo'llari bir-biriga yaqinlasha boshladi. Ilmiy natijalarni jamiyatda foydalanish uchun texnologiya bilan bog'lash kontseptsiyasi taxminan 1850-yillardan keyin keng tarqaldi, ya'ni kimyo haqidagi bilimlardan foydalanishga asoslangan kimyo sanoati rivojlana boshladi va elektromagnetizm haqidagi bilimlarga asoslangan elektrotexnika texnologiyalari paydo bo'ldi. Ilm-fan intellektual dunyo biznesidan uzoqlashdi, ilmiy natijalar endilikda ham makon, ham vaqt nuqtai nazaridan inson faoliyatining chegaralarini ochib berdi va inson faoliyati imkoniyatlarini kengaytirdi. Yigirmanchi asrning eng yirik olimlaridan biri Albert Eynshteyn ketma-ket foton nazariyasini e'lon qilganida, tarixdagi eng hayratlanarli yillardan biri edi. Broun harakati nazariyasi va maxsus nisbiylik nazariyasi, bularning barchasi o'sha paytdagi fizika qarashlarini o'zgarishi uchun xizmat qilgan.

So'nggi yillardagi IT inqilobi kompyuter texnologiyalaridagi ko'plab ishlanmalarning, jumladan, Alan Turing tomonidan taklif qilingan hisoblash mashinasi kontseptsiyasi va Uilyam Shokli, Jon Bardin va Uolter Brattain tomonidan tranzistor ixtirosi, shuningdek, paydo bo'lishining cho'qqisi hisoblanadi. Internet va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridagi boshqa yutuqlar. Biroq, IT inqilobi nafaqat yangi mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqish yoki odamlarning qulayliklarini yaxshilashdan iborat emas, balki butun dunyo odamlariga kibertexnologiyalardan foydalanish uchun ochilgan imkoniyatlar orqali odamlarning xatti-harakatlari va turmush tarzini tubdan o'zgarishiga olib keldi. Ilm-fanning zamonaviy sivilizatsiyaning o'rnatilishiga qo'shgan hissasining yana bir jihati ilm-fan taraqqiyoti bilan ilmiy tafakkur dunyosiga doimiy ravishda tarqalishidir. Zamonaviy ilm-fanning dunyo bo'ylab tarqalishi tarixi mamlakatlar va mintaqalar bo'yicha keskin o'zgarib turadi. Ilmiy natijalar yangi mahsulotlar va yangi texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish bilan bog'liq bo'lib, iqtisodiy va tibbiy taraqqiyotga, boshqa real ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy faoliyatga katta hissa qo'shadi. Ilmiy natijalar haqiqiy, foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan mahsulot va

xizmatlarni yaratishi mumkin bo'lgan texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish bilan bog'liqmi yoki yo'qmi, muhim nuqtai nazardir.

Tadqiqot xarajatlari va tadqiqot asbob-uskunalari, jihozlari va tadqiqot muhitining boshqa jihatlarini rivojlantirish tadqiqot va ishlanmalarni rag'batlantirish uchun muhim bo'lsada, eng asosiy talab tadqiqotchilarni ijodiy qobiliyatga ega bo'lgan holda tarbiyalashdir. Tadqiqot va ishlanmalarda fundamental tadqiqotlarda tadqiqotchilar o'z tashabbusi bilan ijodiy mavzularni ko'rib chiqishga mos xarakterga ega bo'lishi va tadqiqotchi inson resurslarini ijodiy qobiliyatlarga ega bo'lishi kerak. Fundamental tadqiqotlarni rag'batlantirish inson resurslarini rivojlantirish nuqtai nazaridan ham muhim hisoblanadi. Asosiy tadqiqotlar va boshqa ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari natijasida olingan yangi bilimlarni amaliy qo'llanmalar bilan mustahkam bog'lash ham muhimdir.

Universitetlar va boshqa davlat ilmiy-tadqiqot muassasalarida olingan fundamental tadqiqotlar va boshqa ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari natijalari texnologiya va amaliy qo'llanmalar bilan mustahkam bog'lanishi uchun sanoat, ilmiy doiralar va hukumat o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Fundamental tadqiqotlar va boshqa ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari natijasida yaratilgan yangi bilimlar tegishli himoya bilan ta'minlanishi va shu bilan birga jamiyat ulardan maksimal darajada foydalanishi uchun joylashtirilishi kerak. Mahsulot ishlab chiqarishning yuqori texnologiyalari ko'p jihatdan individual ko'nikmalarga tayanadi, masalan, individual qo'lda texnologiyalar va mahalliy texniklarning stanoklar va metall qoliplarni ishlab chiqarishdagi ko'nikmalari hamda muammolarni aniqlash va ularga javob berish uchun texnik va malakali bilimlarni to'plash. Ushbu texnologiyalar va ko'nikmalarni kelgusida o'tkazish va ular bilan bog'liq inson resurslarini mustahkam saqlash va tarbiyalash muhimdir. An'anaviy texnologiya va ko'nikmalar eng ilg'or texnologiyalar bilan bog'lanib, yangi taraqqiyotni rag'batlantirmoqda. Ilm-fan va texnologiya umuman insoniyatning turmush darajasini yaxshilashga yordam bergan bo'lsada, bu millatlar o'rtasidagi tafvutning kengayishiga yordam beradi.

Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda iqtisodiy rivojlanishning o'ziga xos belgisi bo'lgan ommaviy ishlab chiqarishni, ommaviy iste'molni va ommaviy chiqindilarni hamma hududlarda targ'ib qilishga bo'lgan har qanday urinish jismoniy cheklangan chunki resurslar tezda tugaydi va atrof-muhit vayron bo'ldi. Natijada, kelajak avlodlar uchun go'zal yashash muhitini qoldirish, o'z avlodimizning turmush darajasini saqlab qolish va rivojlantirishni maqsad qilgan rag'batlantirishda ilm-fan va texnologiyaning roli tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Inson resurslarini qo'llab-quvvatlash, ilmiy-texnikaviy texnologiyalar bilan bog'liq boshqa tadbirlar orqali atrof-muhit siyosatini shakllantirish va amalga oshirishni qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun aniq sa'y-harakatlarni amalga oshirmoqda. Ilm-fan va texnologiya ham jahon iqtisodiy o'sishi, ham global atrof-muhitni saqlashning kaliti ekanligini e'lon qildi. Odamlar hayoti xavfsizligi va farovonligini mustahkamlash hamda mamlakatimizning barqaror o'sishini ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligini tan oldi. Jamiyat uchun fan va texnologiyaning xalqaro jamiyatga qo'shgan hissasi va xalqaro ishtirokini namoyish qilish siyosatidan biri sifatida juda muhim deb qaralishi kerak.

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МНОГОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ИЗМЕРИТЕЛЬНЫЕ ПРЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛИ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ЖИДКИХ СРЕД ДЛЯ СИСТЕМ КОНТРОЛЯ, УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И МОНИТОРИНГА

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Аннотация: *излагаются вопросы создания, исследования технических возможностей и развития научно-методологической базы проектирования многофункциональных первичных измерительных преобразователей параметров жидких дисперсных сред очистных сооружений и водоемов, предназначенных для использования в системах контроля, управления и мониторинга.*

Ключевые слова: *многофункциональные измерительные преобразователи, очистные сооружения и водоемы, системы контроля, управления и мониторинга.*

Большинство жидкостей в природе и технике существует в виде жидких дисперсных сред (ЖДС): эмульсий, суспензий, коллоидных растворов. Информация о концентрации взвешанных частиц дисперсной (ДФ) зачастую важна для контроля и управления многими технологическими процессами, а также для экологического мониторинга. Наиболее типичными примерами объектов, требующих исправного контроля концентрации дисперсной среды в жидких средах являются [1]:

- контроль качества питьевой воды на всех этапах и подготовки;
- контроль физико-технических параметров сточных вод;
- контроль технологического процесса осаждения взвеси в резервуарах-отстойниках систем химводоочистки теплоэлектро-станций;
- измерение и контроль концентрации взвешенных частиц органического и неорганического происхождения в технике, биологии и медицине.

Измерения концентрации дисперсных жидких сред в промышленных условиях обладают своей специфической и отличаются от условий лабораторных измерений. Получается при этом информация используется либо при пассивном наблюдении и мониторинга, либо для формирования целенаправленного воздействия на исследуемый объект. Цель воздействия может состоять в оптимизации исследуемого технологического процесса, предотвращения аварийных ситуаций и т.п. Уровень приведенной погрешности измерения концентрации может сказаться достаточным. Между тем уровень приведенной погрешности для лабораторных средств должен быть значительно ниже. То же самое относится и к быстрдействию измерения конструкции при однократности измерении концентрации, как правило, достаточен, как и в предыдущем случае практических измерений, в то время как данный показатель применительно к показателю быстрдействия почти на порядок ниже; обычно продолжительность однократного измерения от десятых долей секунды до нескольких секунд, что вполне приемлемо. Однако для полевых измерителей концентрации первостепенную важность имеют эксплуатационные и надежные показатели.

Часто полевые измерения проводятся в жестких условиях: в непрерывном потоке с большим расходом контролируемой жидкости, при больших давлениях, в условиях коррозионной активности среды, абразивной или липкой дисперсной среды и изменяющейся дисперсности частиц, наличие паразитных отложений солей или вязких фракций среды на датчиках. Дисперсная среда, как правило, может быть многофазной, может содержать фазу из пузырьков свободного газа, что дополнительно усложняет

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измерения. При этом доступ к датчикам часто затруднен или даже невозможен без остановки технологического процесса [2].

При подобных условиях весьма важна высокая надежность и в особой степени метрологическая надежность средств измерений концентрации первичными преобразователями. Потребители средств измерения концентрации жидких дисперсных сред заинтересованы в значительном круге измерительных преобразователей наподобие показателей: период последовательной работы, метповерочный материал, средняя наработка на отказ, средний срок службы и т.д.

Наиболее успешно в настоящее время используются полевые контроллеры жидких дисперсных сред, принцип действия которых основан на рассеянии различных зондирующих излучений (в первую очередь, радиоволновых, оптических и акустических). К примеру, для измерения концентрации разбавленных эмульсий и суспензий используют нефелометрический и турбидиметрический методы, входящих в группу фотоэлектрических методов и основанных на взаимодействии оптического излучения с частицами дисперсной среды [3].

Для определения содержания газовой среды в жидкостях весьма эффективен акустические методы. Однако известные концентраторы не обладают достаточной стойкостью к действию возмущающих воздействий, а для поддержания необходимого уровня метрологической надежности требуется частое вмешательство обслуживающего персонала.

Существуют технологические и технические предпосылки для повышения надежности средств измерений концентрации контролируемых жидких сред. Перспективным направлением в этой среде является использование мультисенсорных структур, широкое практическое применение встраиваемой микропроцессорной техники, интеллектуализация алгоритмов работы и т.д. однако до сих пор не созданы измерительные преобразователи для полевых измерений концентрации жидких сред, которые удовлетворяли бы всем современным требованиям к средствам индустриальной автоматизации. По всей видимости, причина состоит в не комплексном применении всего арсенала методов современных информационно-измерительных технологий, в недостаточно развитой теоретической базе решения подобных задач и отсутствие обоснованных и хорошо проработанных методов проектирования. В этой связи существует настоятельная необходимость разработки на основе общей концепции построения высоконадежных полевых концентраторов жидких сред, создания и исследования новых первичных измерительных преобразователей концентрации жидких сред, создания и исследования новых первичных измерительных преобразователей концентрации жидких дисперсных сред различного назначения, обладающих улучшенными надежностными и эксплуатационными метрологическими характеристиками.

Одним из наиболее применимых для промышленных измерений концентрации дисперсной среды жидких сред являются фотометрические преобразователи, измеряющие мутность – величину, которая характеризует способность жидкой среды рассеивать свет на частицах дисперсной среды. Соответствующие контрольно-измерительные приборы, именуемые мутномеры, подразделяются на два вида – турбидиметры и нефелометры. Градуироваться мутномеры могут как в единицах концентрации дисперсной среды, так и единицах мутности [4].

Основной трудностью при эксплуатации датчиков мутности являются паразитные отложения на прозрачных окнах излучателей и фотоприемников, которые постоянно накапливаются и приводят к искажению результатов и к метрологическому отказу. При этом доступ к датчикам часто затруднен или невозможен без остановки технологического процесса, а их обслуживание может быть сопряжено со значительными материальными,

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временными и трудовыми затратами. Проблема обычно усугубляется тем, что мутномеры рассчитаны на определенный диапазон концентраций. Для широкодиапазонных измерений мутности требуются адаптивная перестройка геометрических параметров мутномера и алгоритма его функционирования.

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МНОГОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ПРЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛИ ДЛЯ СИСТЕМЫ КОНТРОЛЯ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РЕЖИМАМИ ПОДВОДНОГО АГРЕГАТА ОЧИСТКИ ДОННЫХ ОТЛОЖЕНИЙ В ВОДОЕМАХ

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Аннотация. *Основной проблемой на сегодняшний день является уменьшение объема воды в водоемах за счет заполнения их дна илом. Причинами являются поступление взвешенных наносов с водозабора, ветровой перенос летучих песков с суши, выпадение в осадок химических соединений, биомассы водной растительности, размыв берегов волновыми процессами. Создание инновационной технологии очистки донных отложений водоохраных сооружений и каналов является важнейшей задачей на сегодняшний день.*

В настоящее время мы работаем над инновационным подходом к решению своего рода задачи по разработке системы управления очисткой донных отложений в водохранилищах и магистральных каналах, построенной на современной программно-аппаратной базе. Позволяющий обеспечить дистанционное управление с высокой точностью и при этом не требующий больших затрат электроэнергии, воды и финансовых средств, что позволит увеличить объем воды, продезинфицировать дно для реактивации донной флоры и фауны, сохранить чистоту воды, а также усовершенствовать существующие системы управления, является актуальной задачей.

Ключевые слова: *водоем, очистное устройство, донные отложения, мониторинг и управление, многофункциональные преобразователи, вода.*

В настоящее время в мире вопросы автоматизации процессов подводных агрегатов очистки является несомненным условием обеспечения рентабельности, в том числе повышения их эффективности и конкурентоспособности. Прежде всего, это обусловлено необходимостью достижения лучшего качества водных ресурсов, поддержания водных каналов в чистоте, обеззараживания дна, реактивации донной флоры и фауны, повышения производительности, внедрения и развития новых более эффективных методов очистки и обеспечения заданными значениями режимами агрегата. Решение данных вопросов требует также повышения достоверности контроля режимов подводного агрегата в управлении различным технологическим оборудованием при современных масштабах производства с использованием соответствующих средств автоматизации. Одним из наиболее интенсивно развивающихся является оптоволоконный метод контроля и управления режимами подводного агрегата очистки донных отложений в водных каналах [1].

В мире проводятся научно-исследовательские работы, направленные на получение точных сведений о различных параметрах и свойствах в процессе контроля и управления режимом подводного агрегата. Одним из основных требований, предъявляемым к измерительным преобразователям является объединение единства измерений, в связи с этим большое значение уделяется совершенствованию многофункциональных преобразователей параметров давления, температуры, уровня, скорости вращения двигателя в процессах контроля и управления режимами подводного агрегата очистки донных отложений [2].

В республике осуществляется внедрение передовых инновационных технологий в водное хозяйство, реализация высокоэффективных систем контроля и управления качеством водных ресурсов с применением современных технических средств

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микропроцессоров с использованием оптоволоконных световодов. Для реализации задач контроля и управления режимами подводного агрегата весьма перспективны многофункциональные преобразователи температуры, уровня, давления, скорости вращения двигателя, установленных в виде прибора на одной несущей конструкции. В связи с этим разработка многофункциональных преобразователей систем контроля и управления режимами подводного агрегата очистки донных отложений в водных каналах является современной актуальной задачей.

При изучении донных отложений в водных каналах, основное внимание уделяется их физико-механическим свойствам и характеру взаимодействия с рабочими органами очистителя. Для сравнения различных грунтов друг с другом их свойства оцениваются численными величинами, то есть показателями. Эти показатели не являются физическими константами, так как их значения изменяются в зависимости от условий, в которых находятся донные отложения.

Различаются два класса показателей:

К первому относят физико-механические показатели, которые непосредственно используются в расчетных формулах; ко второму относят физические показатели, которые характеризуют грунты по их составу [3]. В эксплуатационных условиях в зависимости от различных факторов механические характеристики грунтов могут испытывать относительные изменения как в сторону снижения, так и повышения, и эту возможность необходимо учитывать при проектировании новых рабочих органов.

Рассмотрим механические характеристики грунтов донных отложений, их влияние на рабочий процесс очистных работ. В природных условиях грунты встречаются в различных физических состояниях: песчаные – от плотного до рыхлого, глинистые – от твердого до текучего. Грунты в зависимости от их состояния и физико-механических свойств, по разному воздействуют на рабочий очистной орган. Так, объемная масса грунта влияет на затраты энергии при подъеме и его транспортировании; сопротивление грунта сдвигу воздействует на тяговое усилие машины; влажность грунта влияет на коэффициент трения грунта об элементы рабочего органа; сопротивление грунта резанию создает внешние усилия на навесное оборудование и разворачивающий момент базы машины и т.д.

На основе анализа проб наносных отложений, взятых из водных каналов, установлено, что количество частиц размером менее 0,1 мм 13 составляет более 70%. Это существенно влияет на липкость грунта на режущие элементы рабочего органа. Объемная масса наносного слоя в период весенней очистки (март-апрель) изменяется в пределах от 1,6 до 1,8 г/см³ (16...18 Н/см³); плотность по ударнику ДорНИИ от 1,5 до 6 ударов, а в период осенней очистки (октябрь-ноябрь) плотность составляет 0,7...2 удара [4].

Физико-механические показатели наносного слоя свидетельствуют о том, что данные грунты являются либо абразивными – песок, либо энергоемкими по разработке – суглинистые, глинистые.

Практика эксплуатации водных каналов показывает, что они заилятся и зарастают полностью по всему сечению. Поэтому, для снижения энергозатрат по удалению донного слоя грунта из водных каналов целесообразно создание такого рабочего органа, который производит очистку водных каналов с переменной площадью срезания стружки, оптимальной за один проход и максимальной – за минимальное количество проходов.

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NUTQNI TANISH TEXNOLOGIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqola hozirgi kunda nutqani aniqlash tizimlari bilan bog'liq. Ushbu maqolada nutqni aniqlash texnologiyalari haqida batafsil keltirilgan. Nutqni aniqlash texnologiyasi neyron tarmoqlari asosida amalga oshiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Nutqni aniqlash, nutqni aniqlash texnologiyasi, telefoniya, maishiy texnika, MANGO OFFICE nutq tahlili tizimi.

Nutqni aniqlash tizimi - bu odamning nutqini matnga aylantirish mumkin bo'lgan texnologiya. U avtonom tarzda ishlashi yoki ma'lum bir foydalanuvchining talaffuz xususiyatlarini o'rganishi mumkin. Ovozni aniqlash nutqni aniqlash texnologiyasining bir qismidir. Spiker identifikatsiyasi shaxsiy fayllarga kirishni cheklash uchun biometrik tekshirishda qo'llaniladi. Tizim odamning ovozini eslab qoladi va uni boshqa ovozlardan ajratib turadi.

Nutqni aniqlash texnologiyasi yoki Nutqdan matnga (ovozdan matnga) o'tgan asrning oxirida paydo bo'lgan, ammo dasturlar IT texnologiyalari va mashinani o'rganishning rivojlanishi bilan faqat 2000-yillarda inson nutqini sifatli matnga aylantirishni o'rgangan. . Bugungi kunda nutqni aniqlash tizimlari kundalik hayotda va biznesda keng qo'llaniladi, chunki u resurslarni sezilarli darajada tejaydi.

Bu murakkab ko'p bosqichli algoritm, shuning uchun biz ishlashning umumiy printsiptini tasvirlashga harakat qilamiz. Agar siz ovozli qidiruvga "Aleksandr Pushkin" deb aytsangiz, telefon taniqli yozuvchining ismini eshitmaydi, lekin aniq chegaralarsiz ovozli signal. Tizim ushbu doimiy signaldan shaxs tomonidan takrorlangan iborani quyidagicha qayta tuzadi:

- Birinchidan, qurilma ovozli so'rovni yozib oladi va neyron tarmoq nutq oqimini tahlil qiladi. Ovoz to'lqini bo'laklarga - fonemalarga bo'linadi.

- Keyin neyron tarmoq shablonlarini ko'rib chiqadi va fonemalarni harf, bo'g'in yoki so'z bilan moslashtiradi. Keyinchalik, dasturga ma'lum bo'lgan so'zlardan tartib tuziladi va u kontekstga muvofiq noma'lum so'zlarni kiritadi. Ushbu ikki bosqichdagi ma'lumotlarni birlashtirish natijasida nutqdan matnga tarjima olinadi.

Rivojlanishning boshida nutqdan matnga ishlash jarayoni elementar akustik modeldan iborat edi - inson nutqi naqshlar bilan taqqoslangan . Ammo tizimdagi lug'atlar soni aniq tanib olish uchun etarli emas edi, dastur ko'pincha xatolarga yo'l qo'ydi.

Neyron tarmoqlarni o'rgatish qobiliyati tufayli nutqni aniqlash sifati sezilarli darajada oshdi. Algoritm jonli nutqdagi so'zlarning odatiy ketma-ketligini biladi va tilning tuzilishini idrok eta oladi - til modeli shunday ishlaydi. Va har bir yangi qayta ishlangan ovozli ma'lumot keyingisining qayta ishlash sifatiga ta'sir qiladi va xatolar sonini kamaytiradi.

Nutqni aniqlash texnologiyasi bizga kerakli ma'lumotlarni qidirish, navigator yordamida marshrutni yaratish imkonini beradi. Nutqdan matnga foydalanish hayotni osonlashtirgan yana bir nechta sohalar :

- Telefoniya. Texnologiya nafaqat qo'ng'iroq qiluvchining vaqtini, balki kompaniya resurslarini ham tejaydi. Ovozli terish va robot yordamida mijozlar menejerlar ishtirokisiz tovarlarga buyurtma berishlari, so'rovlarga javob berishlari va maslahatlar olishlari mumkin.

- Maishiy texnika va shaxsiy kompyuter. Bugungi kunda siz turli xil qurilmalarni ovozingiz bilan boshqarishingiz mumkin: kalitlar, yoritish tizimlari va gadjetlar. Siz kompyuteringizni ovozingizni taniy olishga o'rgatishingiz mumkin (Windows va Mac tizimlarida)

- Dori-darmon. 2020-yilda rossiyalik ishlab chiquvchilar tibbiy hujjatlarni to'ldiradigan sun'iy intellektga asoslangan Voice2Med tizimini yaratdilar.

Nutqni aniqlash sizga savdo va mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatish nazoratidan tortib, firibgarlikdan himoyalashgacha bo'lgan ko'plab biznes jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirish imkonini

beradi.

Ushbu texnologiyadan foydalangan holda, mijozlar bilan telefon suhbatlari tahlili osonroq va arzonlashdi: tizim avtomatik ravishda qo'ng'iroqlarni yozib oladi va konversiyani oshirish uchun ma'lumotlarni to'playdi.

Misol uchun, MANGO OFFICE nutq tahlili tizimi xaridorlar mahsulotlarni qaysi raqobatchilar bilan tez-tez solishtirishini aniqlashga yordam beradi. Odatda, raqobatchilarni eslatish uchun teglar yaratiladi, suhbat hisobotlarini tahlil qilinadi va marketing strategiyasini qanday yaxshilash kerakligi tushunib olinadi. Shuningdek, xodimlarning ishini tahlil qilish mumkin - to'xtash so'zlari belgilanadi, savdo skriptlariga muvofiqligi nazorat qilinadi. Agar videodan nutqni transkripsiya qilish kerak bo'lsa, undan audio faylni yuklab olish va uni nutq tahlili xizmatiga yuklash mumkin. Videodagi nutq aniq bo'lishi muhim, shuning uchun videoda gapirganda mikrofondan foydalanish lozim.

Nutqni tahlil qilish biznesni rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan yana bir soha - bu interaktiv ovozli tizimlar (IVR) . Bu qo'ng'iroqlar markazini boshqarishda ajralmas vositadir. Speech - to - Text mijozning nutqini taniydi va ovozli robot avtomatik ravishda javob uchun kerakli ma'lumotlarni tanlaydi yoki qo'ng'iroqni operatorga uzatadi. Texnologiya yo'qolgan qo'ng'iroqlar sonini kamaytiradi, chunki ko'pchilikning vaqti yo'q yoki ovozli menyudagi tugmalarni bosa olmaydi.

Xizmatni nazorat qilish xizmatlari qo'shimcha so'rovlar o'tkazishi shart emas: bu avtomatik ravishda amalga oshirilishi mumkin, keyin esa hisobotlarni tahlil qilish. Banklardagi xavfsizlik xizmatlari mijozlarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish uchun nutq tahlilidan foydalanadi.

Xulosa. Ovozdan matnga texnologiya kundalik vazifalarni soddalashtiradi va ko'plab professional sohalarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Biznesda Speech - to- Text mijozlar bilan samarali muloqot qilish va katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni tezda qayta ishlash uchun ishlatiladi. Analitik va ovozli robotlar xarajatlarni kamaytiradi, o'rtacha chekni oshiradi va mijozlarning haqiqiy ehtiyojlarini o'rganadi. Nutq tahlili qo'ng'iroqlarni boshqarishni avtomatlashtiradi va vaqtni tejaydi. Odatda sotuvga o'tish amalga oshiriladi, xizmat ko'rsatish sifati yaxshilanadi va bozordan tushunarli tilda fikr-mulohaza olinadi.

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FAN-TEXNIKA TARAQQIYOT TARIXI VA IJTIMOY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI**Dilshodov Abrorjon Dilshodjon o'g'li***Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg'ona filiali katta o'qituvchisi***Rustamova Parizoda***Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg'ona filiali AKT sohasida kasb ta'limi yo'nalishi 622-21 guruh talabasi*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola fan-texnika taraqqiyot tarixi va rivojlanish sabablari, ijtimoiy-huquqiy asoslari haqida.

Kalit so'zlar: Fan, texnika, ijtimoiy-huquqiy asoslar, FTT, ITT.

Fan-texnika taraqqiyoti [FTT] – bu fan va texnikaning oldinga siljishi, tabiatdagi tashqi kuchlarni o'rganish va o'zlashtirish asosida ishlab chiqaruvchi kuchlarining barcha elementlarini evolyutsion rivojlanishi: moddiy ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirishning ob'ektiv, doimiy faoliyat yurituvchi muntazamligi bo'lib, uning natijasi texnologiya va ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etishning izchil takomillashtirilishi va ularning samaradorligini oshirishdir.

Insoniyat iqtisodining asosiy qonunlaridan biri ijtimoiy ishlab chiqarishning bosqichma-bosqich rivojlanishi, uning doimiy takomillashib borishidir. Ular ilm-fan va texnika taraqqiyotiga asoslanadi.

Insoniyat sivilizatsiyasining ming yilliklari davomida ilmiy-texnikaviy taraqqiyot murakkab va ziddiyatli rivojlanish yo'lini bosib o'tdi. Bu jamiyat taraqqiyotining dastlabki bosqichlarida 18-asr oxiri - 19-asr boshlarigacha ilmiy taraqqiyotdan alohida amalga oshirilgan texnik taraqqiyot bilan bog'liq edi. Sanoat inqilobi davridagina ilmiy-texnika taraqqiyotining tez yaqinlashuvi boshlandi va yaxlit ilmiy-texnikaviy taraqqiyot (ITT) vujudga keldi. Shu vaqtdan boshlab fanni bevosita ishlab chiqaruvchi kuchga aylantirish jarayoni boshlandi, u taxminan bir yarim asr davom etdi va 1950-yillarning o'rtalarida ilmiy-texnikaviy inqilob rivojlanishi bilan yakunlandi.

2019-yilda tadqiqotchilar bir necha o'n yillar ichida ilmiy-texnikaviy taraqqiyot (ITT) o'ziga xos xususiyati misli ko'rilmagan sur'atdir. Bu raqamli va infokommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq. Texnologik rivojlanish tezligini va natijada ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va infratuzilmaviy o'zgarishlarni inson hayoti bilan o'zaro bog'lash bizga rivojlanish tezligida sifat oshishiga imkon beradi, bu yangi vaqtinchalik davrga o'tishni anglatadi. Real vaqt rejimida tub o'zgarishlar ro'y bermoqda va insoniyat o'z tarixida hech qachon duch kelmagan misli ko'rilmagan imkoniyatlar va muammolarni yuzaga keltirmoqda.

Dastlabki fan rivoji bilan texnika taraqqiyoti o'rtasidagi yaqinlashuv 16—18-asrlarda manufaktura ishlab chiqarishi bilan bog'liq holda sodir bo'lgan. 16-asrda savdo-sotiq va yirik manufaktura davri tub o'zgarishlar bir qancha aniq vazifalarni nazariy va eksperimental hal qilishni talab qildi. Bu davrda fan uyg'onish davri g'oyalari ta'sirida sxolastika an'analarini parchalab, amaliyotga murojaat qildi. Kompas, porox va kitob nashr qilish ilmiy-texnikaviy faoliyatga asos solgan 3 ta yirik kashfiyot bo'ldi.

- **1-bosqich:** Suv tegirmonlarining rivojlanayotgan manufaktura ishlab chiqarishida qo'llanilishi ba'zi mexanik jarayonlarni nazariy tadqiq etishni talab qildi. Natijada charxpalak g'ildiragi, charxpalak harakati nazariyasi, qarshilik va ishqalanish ta'limotlari yaratildi.
- **2-bosqich:** Mashina ishlab chiqarishning 18-asr oxiridan boshlab taraqqiy etishi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, bunda fan bilan texnika bir-birining jadal rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Bu davrda ilmiy tadqiqot faoliyatida nazariy masalalarni hayotga tatbiq qilishga da'vat etuvchi

fanning maxsus bo'g'inlari paydo bo'ldi: amaliy tadqiqotlar, ishlab chiqarish tadqiqotlari, amaliy konstruktiv ishlanmalar va h.k.

- **3-bosqich:** an-texnika inqilobi bilan bog'liq. Uning ta'sirida texnika taraqqiyotiga qaratilgan ilmiy sohalar kengaydi. Texnik masalalarni hal qilishda biologlar, fiziologlar, psixologlar, mantiqshunoslar ishtirok etdi. Fan-texnika taraqqiyoti, shuningdek, ijtimoiy fanlar yo'nalishlari, iqtisod va ishlab chiqarishni tashkil qilish, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy jarayonlarni ilmiy boshqarish, aniq ijtimoiy tadqiqotlar kabilarga bilvosita ta'sir qildi. Fanning texnikaga nisbatan yetakchilik mavqei yanada yorqin namoyon bo'ladi, fan texnikani uzluksiz inqiloblashtiruvchi kuchga aylandi. O'z navbatida, texnika ham fan taraqqiyotiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatib, uning oldiga yangi talab va vazifalar qo'ydi. Hozirgi zamon fantexnika inqilobining xarakterli xususiyati uning sanoat bilan birga ijtimoiy hayotning turli sohalarini: qishloq xo'jaligi, transport, aloqa, tibbiyot, ta'lim, maishiy xizmat kabilarni qamrab olganligidadir.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytamizki zamon o'zgargan sari fan va texnika tarqqiydashib boraveradi. Har bir davrning o'ziga xos talablari va takliflari mavjuddir. Aynan shundan kelib chiqib yangi-yangi izlanish, tajriba va kashfiyotlar shakllanib, yaralib boradi. Bularning barchasi, albatta insoniyat bilan bevosita bog'liqdir. Inson yashash davomida har doim nimagadir ehtiyoj sezadi. Shu ehtiyojdan kelib chiqib izlanadi va uni yaratadi. Aynan shu o'rganish va yaratishlar natijasida esa fan-texnika rivojlanib boraveradi.

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MILITARY ADMINISTRATION AND THE STRUCTURE OF THE ARMY IN THE KOKAND KHANATE

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Abstract. In this article the Kokand Khanate, one of the biggest khanates in Central Asia ruled in 1710-1876, the role of its military system in the social, political and economical life was described. The article mainly focuses on the analysis of the formation of the military administrative system in the khanate, its lower, middle and higher ranks, material and technical supply of the army and the achievements and faults of the military administration on the basis of the historical sources and archival documents.

Key words: statehood, Kokand khanate, military affair, arms, administrative procedures, domestic policy, foreign policy, positions, high level, middle level, low level, fortresses, beys, commandant, commander in chief, amirlashkar, clothing.

Actuality of the research. From the point of view of the history of statehood, military affair is an integral part of the country's domestic and foreign policy. In the history of Central Asia, the military field has always been in the focus of attention of the rulers. They relied on military forces, which were an important factor in the implementation of their domestic and foreign policies. Over the centuries, a certain system of controlling these forces, its various branches have been formed. Accordingly, the scope of positions to be given to those responsible for maintaining the military power of the state was also determined.

Methods of the research. The article is based on generally accepted historical methods such as the principles of historicity, comparability, consistency and objectivity.

The results of the research. The military system formed over the centuries retained its main features in the first half of the XVIII-XIX centuries. This can be observed by analyzing the military positions and the responsibilities of their owners that existed in the Kokand Khanate during the period being studied. Although there was no special cabinet in the field of military administration in Central Asia before the Kokand Khanate, especially in the state of Amir Temur, there were different military officials and the tasks assigned to them by the state were clearly systematized. Based on the data of historical sources, it can be observed that there were three categories of military ranks and titles in the Kokand khanate - high, medium and low.

The high military ranks and titles included mingbashi, amirlashkar, kushbegi (*hist. head vizier or official of similar stature in a khan's court*), batirbashi, voliy (deputy), qal'aban, qurbashi (*hist. custodian of arms of a khan; a high military title during the khanate period; chief of police in the territory of Turkistan; commander of a group of basmachis*), yovar, tupchibashi, to'qsoba, ponsodbashi.

The middle ranks and titles were yuzbashi (*hist. commander of 100 cavalry*), ellikbashi (*hist. military rank of officer in charge of 40-50 cavalry; title of prerevolutionary minor official*), dahbashi (*hist. commander of 10 men*), korovulbegi (*hist. captain of the guard*).

The lower-level military ranks and titles consisted of soldiers, sarboz (*hist. footsoldiers*), navkars (soldiers), mergans (sharpshooters, archers), mahrams (secretary), botur, jazoilchi, guardians and guards.

The candidates for these positions and titles were appointed by the khan. The analysis of historical sources indicates that the representatives of all classes and clans in the khanate could get various military ranks and titles. As H. Bobobekov noted, in the Kokand khanate mainly Uzbek representatives were appointed to the administrative and military positions from the first to the seventh level [1, p. 43]. These views of the scientist are not confirmed in all sources. As the written sources indicated, in the 50s and 60s of the XIX century, the Tajik Shadi, the Kyrgyz Alikuli were

appointed to the highest military position of mingbashi, and the Lashkarbeklarbegi, a slave, was appointed as the governor of Tashkent.

The highest of the military ranks and titles in the khanate was the mingbashi. The mingbashi was the commander of a thousand soldiers. As an administrator, he was the governor of the property given by a thousand soldiers. In the Kokand khanate he was the second person after the khan. According to the historical sources, this position was introduced in the Kokand khanate during the reign of Alimkhan. About the duties of the mingbashi, Mulla Alim Mahdum Haji said: "... this position is in the ranks of the military ministry, and can interfere in all the affairs of the governments, including foreign and domestic affairs" [2, p. 104]. It is obvious from that the mingbashi was a person with unlimited power after the khan. In the Bukhara Emirate this duty was performed by the kushbegi (*hist. head vizier or official of similar stature in a khan's court*).

In the khanate, the mingbashi served as a supreme commander. During the military marches, the mingbashi was also given the title of amirlashkar, and all the active troops of the khanate were subordinated to him. The following information of V. P. Nalivkin, who lived in Kokand and wrote his experiences, also confirms it: "Sarboz (Footsoldiers) and artillerymen who lived in Kokand were only under the permanent control of a special deputy, the dodhoh. During the war, the deputy, the dodhoh, received all the soldiers of the army in his unit and handed over the temporary command to a specially appointed amirlashkar (commander-in-chief)" [3, p. 209].

It is also confirmed in Hakimkhan ibn Sayyid Masumkhan's book "Muntahab ut-Tawarikh" that all divisions of the army were united under the command of one army during the military operations. The author noted: "Muhammad Alikhan, finding these words the very potential, and ordered "Give everything to Haqquli commander whatever comes from the state". And ordered again, "If anything accompanies us, whether it is the tunqator, or the waiter, or the shigovul (*hist.court official serving as master of ceremonies*), everything is prepared for the war, and all this belongs to Haqquli mingbashi"[4, p. 153]. During the reign of Sultan Sayyidkhan (1863–1865) of the Kokand khanate, Alikuli, a skilled military commander who played an important role in the social and political life of the khanate, constantly retained the title of "amirlashkar" [5, p. 68].

The post of mingbashi was given to only one person in the khanate. In the Kokand khanate, the role of the mingbashi became a high-level position during the reign of Sheralikhan [6, p. 6]. The mingbashi was actively involved in political and economic activities in addition to the military affairs. This can also be seen in the following example. The zakat tax in the amount of 80,000 gold coins, collected by the governor of Tashkent and given to the khan's treasury, was sent to the Kokand khan in cooperation with the pansodbashi and the yuzbashi and handed over to the mingbashi and reported to the khan by the mingbashi [7, p. 134]. Thus, the economic life of the khanate was also under the control of the mingbashi to a certain extent.

As it has been noted above, the post of mingbashi also gave great political rights to the person who held it. The person who held the post of mingbashi tried to appoint his relatives to the high positions in the khanate as much as possible in accordance with the tribal traditions. This can be seen in the activities of the Musulmonkul mingbashi, who played an important role in the administrative system of the Kokand Khanate in the middle of the XIX century. While Musulmonkul mingbashi, who ruled the country on behalf of the father-in-law of Khudoyorkhan, originally came from the Kipchak origin, was holding the position of mingbashi, the Kipchaks were not only appointed to various positions, but also they made up the bulk of the army [8, p. 5].

The unlimited privileges that the position of mingbashi would give to the person who possessed it would naturally lead to a struggle between the different tribes to occupy that position. In the Kokand khanate, a person who occupied the position of mingbashi, in some cases, became the full ruler of the khanate. Musulmonkul, who was the custodian of young Khudoyorkhan, and Aliquli, who was the guardian of Sultan Saidkhan (1863–1865) can be included in such commanders. Historical evidences also confirm that they had unlimited power, and in some cases abused their rights. Musulmonkul left Mallakhan, the brother of the supreme ruler Khudoyorkhan, among the military commanders and gave to him a military unit of 200 Karakalpaks. However, he restricted Mallakhon's rights and appointed Jabborquli Kipchak, from the Kipchaks, as his assistant. In practice,

Tursunov B. (2023). Yosh olimlar, doktorantlar va tadqiqotchilarning onlayn ilmiy forumi. *Military administration and the structure of the army in the kokand khanate*, 19-34. TATUFF-EPAI.

the division was subordinated only to Jabborquli [9, p. 39]. According to archival documents from 1863, Mingbashi Aliquli appointed the governors of all cities and fortresses by his own free will after occupying this position [10, p. 116]. In the system of military ranks and titles of the Kokand khanate, the position of kushbegi occupied the next place after the mingbashi. The holder of this post, which was one of the highest military titles, vied for the position of mingbashi. The author of the book "History of Turkistan" gave the following description of this position with high military status: "The position of Kushbegi, the people in this position are always in the presence of the khan as advisers, or they are awarded as the governor of a large city" [11, p. 104–105]. The people who were appointed to the position of Kushbegi could also govern a separate province. These people were also responsible for the protection of the territories at their disposal, in addition to commanding the provincial military forces entrusted to them. Also, according to Sh. Vahidov this position was often given during the military marches and battles [12, p. 7].

Differing from the Bukhara khanate, four people were appointed to the position of Kushbegi in the Kokand khanate. In most cases, those who hold the position of Kushbegi were appointed the governors of the Tashkent region. The Kushbegi that ruled Tashkent, which played an important economic and political role in the Kokand khanate and was the basis of the defense system on the northern borders of the khanate, had great opportunities. Kushbegi, who was appointed the governor of Tashkent, was superior to other regional governors in terms of military power. In some cases, the governor of Tashkent was given the title of Beklarbegi.

The title of Beklarbegi was given to the supreme Commander-in-Chief during the Timurids period [13, p. 27]. In the Kokand khanate the governor of Tashkent Lashkar beklarbegi was awarded such a title (1810–1812 and 1813–1831). The social origin of the Lashkar beklarbegi was a slave, and was brought to Kokand from Chitrali [14, p. 2]. There are also archival documents from 1861 that the title of Beklarbegi was also awarded to Qanoatshah custodian and that this title was given to him by Mallakhon. According to archival documents this situation was described as following: "Khan Mallabek warmly welcomed the promise of Qanoatshah custodian to allow the Russians to invade other territories and gave him the title of Beklarbegi. He also gave him the garrison and protection of several fortresses included not only in Tashkent region in which he was governing but also in Kokand district in addition to the right of using all the military opportunities in the khanate" [15, p. 132].

Qanoatshah was Tajik and was one of the military and political figures in the Kokand khanate. In 1846–1847 he left for Bukhara after the death of Sarimsakhan, the governor of Tashkent and in 1861–1862 he led the military operations of Kokand army against the Russians, who attacked the fortresses of Turkistan, Yangikurgan, and Julek [16, p. 380]. In other khanates of Central Asia, the duty assigned to the holders of this title was slightly different. In particular, in the Khiva khanate, unlike in Kokand, the beklarbegi was an honorary title given to the elders of Karakalpak and other nomadic peoples [17, p. 246].

One of the most important positions in the military system of the Kokand Khanate was the botirbashi. In the Khanate provinces, there was a unit of more than five hundred soldiers – the botirbashi (a battalion commander) was in charge of the military operations in the province. This is confirmed by the following information about Tashkent. According to it, there were two deputies of the governor of Tashkent, one was the sarkor (a commander) who was in charge of tax collection and civil affairs, and the other was the botirbashi (a battalion commander) of the army [18, p. 10]. The botirbashi was responsible for the training and discipline of the army.

As it was noted above, the army in the provinces obeyed the provincial governor. The governor was in charge of the military and administrative affairs of the province. The deputy of the capital, on the other hand, was responsible for the artillery, that is, the cannon of the moving army, responsible for its preservation and delivery to the destination [19, p. 68].

The qal'aban (Kutvol) was in charge of the fortresses and fortifications located on the borders of the Kokand Khanate, and he was responsible not only for the socio-economic life of these districts, but also for military affairs and border protection. Considering the importance of the fortresses in the khanate's defense system, the people with the title of dodhoh, kushbegi were appointed the qal'aban. The qal'abans of Central fortresses and the commanders of small fortresses were appointed by the

khan. Small fortress commanders were in some cases appointed by provincial governors and commanders as well. The qal'aban of Oqmasjid fortress Yaqubbek Badavlat (1848–1852) was appointed by Normuhammad Kushbegi, and the qal'aban of Yangikurgan fortress Qalandar batir (1864) was appointed by Amirlashkar Alikuli [20, p. 5]. Several military officials worked under the command of the qal'abans. One of them was the military engineers, who were responsible for the construction of the defensive walls of the fortress and the defensive fortifications of army during the wars.

Another position was the Katavuls, who were engaged in the reconstruction and repair of the damaged places of the fortress [21, p. 323]. As it was mentioned above, dodhohs were also appointed to the post of the fortress commandant - the qal'aban. Dodhoh corresponded to the rank of colonel of the Russian military of the XIX century [22, p. 38].

In the military system of the Kokand khanate there was also a position of korboshi, which was engaged in the production and storage of weapons, their delivery to the divisions at the right time. Korboshi was subordinated to the khan and the mingbashi and headed the barracks, the rifle, the artillery. He was also responsible for finding the raw materials and for the production of ready military products [23, p. 8].

Jibachi is also mentioned as the head of the armory store. The documents from the archives of the Kokand khans of the XIX century also confirm that Kurboshi headed the process of arms production. In many of these documents of the 60s of the XIX century Bakhti Muhammad Korboshi was often mentioned. The study of the documents shows that the Kurboshi controlled from the the supply in the workshops to the production process [24, p. 312–313].

In the system of military positions of the Kokand khanate there were different positions and titles, which played an important role in different units of the army, with different responsibilities. These include the yawar, the special guard, the artilleryman, the pansodbashi, the yuzbashi, the ellikbashi, the onbashi, the guard, the qazi askar, the qazi mufti, and the qazi rais. They occupied various positions in the khanate's military system in terms of the duties assigned to them. One of them was yawar, who was also recognized as the head of the amirlashkar's (commander-in-chief) personal detachment, the head of the arms-making workshops. There were usually a hundred men under his control. In some literatures, the Yawar is mentioned as the head of a hundred-man artillery division in the Kokand khanate [25, p. 564]. The personal guards of the Kokand khans were brought up from childhood and trusted persons were appointed as their leaders. Some rulers tried to increase the number of their personal bodyguards.

One archival source from 1874 states that Khudoyorkhan's bodyguards consisted of 400 soldiers who were trained from childhood, and led by three close people of the khan, and a person named Uncle Nasim Kora was appointed as the general supervisor [26, p. 198]. The khan's personal bodyguards were responsible not only for the security of the khan and his family, but also, in some cases, for the security of foreign ambassadors. A. P. Fedchenko wrote that during his stay in the Kokand khanate in 1868–1871, in order to ensure its security, the khan's special personal bodyguards were appointed. The author noted that in addition to the task of guarding, these people were also tasked for inspiring soldiers during the battle, reminding them about their duties [27, p. 38].

In the Khan's army, the head of the artillery unit, who was responsible for its supply and war operations, was the artilleryman. By the 50s and 60s of the XIX century, the weight of artillery in modern warfare had increased. It could also be observed that the external threat, which was dominated by the possession of this type of weapon – Russia's aggressive actions in cases where the Kokand rulers appointed foreign mercenary specialists to lead the artillery.

In the administrative system of the Kokand army there were various officials who headed its various divisions. One of them was the Toqsoba, who was the head of a military detachment having its own flag. He led the army of five hundred men. The Pansodboshi and higher military officials had their own mirzas. Pansod was ranked 16th place among the positions in the Kokand Khanate and ranked second place among the military positions.

According to the authors of the XIX century and archival documents of this period, the army of the Kokand Khanate was respectively divided into five hundred and one hundred. The commander

of infantry division was called the sarbozbashi (footsoldier-captain), and the captain of artillery was the Tupchibashi (artilleryman-captain). In addition to the Pansodbashi and the yuzbashi, there were also ellikbashi and onbashi positions, which were not included in the list of high military ranks (officers). The ordinary soldiers, who were distinguished by their bravery, courage, and ingenuity were appointed to the posts of ellikbashi and onbashi.

Although the children of the Pansodbashi and the Yuzbashi captains began their military careers as ordinary soldiers, they were able to hold the titles of their fathers in the future [28, p. 29]. In a certain sense, military positions were also inherited and passed from father to son. However, in most cases such consistency was not followed. To achieve such a high military position, soldiers also had to have the qualities of courage and resourcefulness to be the model for others.

According to the information given by Sattorkhon Abdulgafforov, if the army revolted against the khan's policy, the lower-ranking military officers were left in their positions [29, p. 29]. These positions were middle-class, and included the Yuzbashi, ellikbashi and onbashi. It is noted that the position of Dahboshi (onboshi) was first used in historical sources in the Kokand army during the reign of Alimkhan, during the siege of Jizzakh (early XIX century) [30, p. 69].

In the Kokand khanate the Karavulbegi was the chief of the guards who guarded the khan's residence at night. The duty of the Karavulbegi was to place and control the guard detachments, to guard the prison. This position existed in other khanates of Central Asia too. In particular, in the Emirate of Bukhara the Darbon did this duty. The Darbon was also involved in the investigation of people who were dangerous to the Emir's authority. The Kushbegi and the Darbon didn't need to leave the arch in any case [31, p. 66].

The Qaziaskar (judge-soldier) dealt with legal issues in the Khanate's army. The Qazi (judge) was a person who made decisions and sentences, and the position of a judge was first introduced during the reign of Caliph Umar (634–644), and from that time the position of a judge-soldier was also introduced [32, p. 125, p. 294]. The Qaziaskar (judge-soldier) was the judge of the military soldiers. When the khan set out on a journey, the judge-soldier accompanied him and personally informed the khan about his affairs abroad as part of his mission [33, p. 276]. The judge-soldier, who was the army judge, declared holy war a “jihad” on behalf of the supreme ruler, assessed the spoils captured, and supervised their proper distribution. The person to be appointed to the military post of the judge-soldier was required to have a good knowledge of military law.

In the book "Shohnomai Nusratpayon" of Mirzo Qalandar Mushrif Isfaghariy it was noted “...The Qaziaskar served in the army and controlled the rules and regulations of Sharia law. It is clear that a well-educated jurist will be appointed to this position” [34, p. 16–17]. During the military operations, the judge of the area where the army was stationed handed over his powers to the judge-soldier. However, as the author of the XVIII century Mirza Badi Devon pointed out, the order of the supreme ruler was needed [35, p. 93]. In addition to serving as a military judge resolving disputes between soldiers, the judge-soldier was also responsible for the moral views of the army. When the military violated discipline, they were subjected to a variety of punitive measures, particularly, flogging was used.

The Qaziaskars (judge-soldiers), in turn, were subordinated to the the chief judicial officer of the country – the Qazikalan (the Judge). The case of the soldiers accused of committing a serious crime, i.e. premeditated murder and treason, was investigated by the Qazikalan (the Judge). They were also sentenced to death in appropriate cases. In addition to the Qaziaskar (judge-soldier), the army also had a position of Qazi-rai (judge-chairman), who oversaw the execution of the fatwa issued by the army mufti.

Law enforcement officials who served in the Khanate's army were responsible for strict adherence to the army morale, laws, and regulations. After all, discipline in the army was the warranty of victory.

From the above information, it can be seen that some administrative and religious positions in the Kokand Khanate were mixed with military ranks. This can also be seen in the following case. The naqib (Arabic - chief, leader, chairman) hodja was a close adviser of the khan, who had graduated from a madrasa and was supposed to be a descendant of the prophet. In official ceremonies, he stood

first on the left side of the khan. At the same time, the naqib hodja had his own soldiers, they took part in the military expeditions [36, p. 183]. This indicates that the military ranks in the khanate were inseparable from the positions in the administration of the government.

Although the system of military administration in the Kokand khanate was similar in many respects to that of the Bukhara and Khiva khanates, it also had its own peculiarities. While the positions of Kushbegi, Devonbegi, Otalik, Parvanachi, and Dadhah were high, in the Kokand Khanate the position of some military officials, especially the Mingbashi, was higher than they. It should be noted here that the Kokand Khanate, like other Central Asian khanates, did not have a centralized system of military administration as in the developed European countries of that time. However, from officials to the ordinary soldier served equally for the security and protection of the country.

In any system of government, the army is a key factor in the implementation of domestic and foreign policy pursued by the supreme head of the central government. The Kokand khanate was no exception.

At this point, naturally the question arises as to what was the army, its structure and composition in the Kokand khanate, and whether its combat was consistent with the implementation of state policy.

While searching the respond to this question, it is necessary to note the following information based on the different sources, literatures and archival documents.

Many Russian travelers and authors of the XIX century argue that the Kokand khanate did not have a regular army, but an irregular army in the khanate, which was gathered only before the marches [37, p. 115]. Indeed, these ideas are not in vain. In the military system of the Kokand khanate there was a large number of auxiliary detachments – “black cherik” and “black cauldron”, which were gathered during the military operations, which outnumbered the regular army. This, in turn, led to the incorrect conclusion that the XX century Russian authors did not have a regular army in the khanate. Similar ideas were reflected in the works of the XX century authors too.

Particularly, A. L. Troitskaya argued that the regular army in the Kokand Khanate was formed during the third reign of Khudoyorkhan (1866–1875), and since then general military obligations had been established [38, p. 138]. He indicated the evidences of the “Russian refugee” in the Kokand khanate, as the confirmation of his opinions, which was written by an unknown author in 1871. It reads the followings: “One of the most difficult obligations in the Kokand Khanate is military service. Khudayarkhan began to establish a regular army in Asian-European style consisting of the soldiers came from neighboring countries and regions, especially, from Bukhara. In doing so, he puts such a weak and small state in a difficult position. Because in the Kokand khanate the population does not know what the general military obligation is. They only know how to arm and fight when it is needed.” The “Russian refugee” also said: “Military service is very heavy in the khanate, and mobilization for military service is not fair. This, in turn, is one of the factors of provoking protests among the people. The Kokand khan, who formed a large army, did not have sufficient funds to provide for the assembled army. As a result, soldiers have to steal and forcibly seize food and eat” [39, p. 29].

This information provided by an unknown author can be evaluated bilaterally. First of all, the author's opinion that the supply of troops in the Kokand khanate was not well organized is quite close to the truth. However, the idea that the regular army in the Kokand khanate was formed by Khudoyorkhan only in the third years of his reign is far from the truth. Because, according to historical data, the fortress and the frontier troops, which existed in the Kokand khanate during the reign of Norbotabiy, served as the basis of the regular army.

The regular army was founded by Kokand khan Alimkhan. During the reign, Alimkhan, nicknamed “Sahibkiran”, formed a special troop consisting of soldiers selected from the existing army and called it galabahadirs or galabatirs. The following information about it was given in the book “History of Turkistan”: “... Alimkhan established peace in the province and in the country, travelled his everywhere in his property and he gathered clever, careful and brave people from everywhere, examined them, made a new notebook, wrote the names of each of them in the notebook, and named them Gala Bahadir” [40, p. 20].

Relying on the organized gala batir guards, Alimkhan was breaking the resistance of the revolting provinces. After that, he formed two divisions consisting of mountaineers who were pleased with their bravery. The first division consisted of 3,700 Qarataghins, and the second division consisted of 2,200 Darvoz, Badakhshan, Shogun, Rushan, "free and slave" Iranians. In the book "Tarihi Shohruhi" this military structure was called the "new army" against the "old army." This military structure was composed of "mir bachchagon" and "bekbachchagon", i.e. the representatives of different regions, and was called the bek's children because they were under the direct leadership of the bek. Until then, the army was called the "black cauldron" and the "black scorpion" [41, p. 95].

Alimkhan marched to Uratepa, relying on the army in the new order. Iriskulbek, Mominbek and Jumaboy Kaytakiy from Karakalpakstan also took part in the march. Although the khan did not like the new army and the new order in general, they wanted to command this army, but the khan kept the command of this army under his control [42, p. 95]. It can be seen from these data that the regular army was formed in the Kokand khanate not in the last years of Khudayarkhan's reign, but in the years of Alimkhan's reign in about 1801.

Historical sources of the XIX century enable us to think about the structure of the army of the Kokand Khanate. According to them, the army of the Kokand Khanate was divided into cavalry, artillery and infantry. In addition to these large divisions, there was a special guard division – the galabatirs and sharpshooter troops.

The main part of the army, that is, the core, was made up of cavalry. According to V. V. Velyaminov-Zernov and A. B. Verevsky, the cavalry was given horses by the government, each valued at up to 80 gold coins [43, p. 115].

F. Nazarov, who was in Kokand in 1813–1814, wrote about keeping horses for 20,000 soldiers in the Kokand khan's stable [44, p. 51]. His following opinions are also noteworthy: "The cavalry soldiers rode on strong horses, wearing expensive coats and red leather trousers. They wore red turbans on their heads. Other types of armies wear white turbans. The uniforms and behavior of the cavalry make impression" [45, p. 50–51]. This view, on the one hand, disproves the view of some researchers that the Kokand cavalry did not have special uniforms [46, p. 139], and, on the other hand, that different military units of the Kokand army had their own uniforms, also indicates that their uniforms were partially different from those of other army types.

Supplying the cavalry and constantly expanding their ranks cost the khanate very expensive. In particular, Khudayarkhan, who was actively involved in military operations in the 60s of the XIX century, in the last years of his reign tried to mobilize the rich people who had their own horses in the cavalry in order to save the khanate's treasury and expand his sphere of influence among the army. According to archival documents, Khudoyorkhan tried to mobilize young men who had strong horses and knew the secrets of riding [47, p. 2014]. The representatives of nomadic Kyrgyz tribes living in the territory of the Kokand Khanate were also mobilized as soldiers to auxiliary cavalry units. Also, according to the procedures introduced in the Kokand Khanate during the height of the military actions, every healthy person was required to come with their horses and take part in military expeditions [48, p. 75].

One of the major components of the army – the infantry division was almost equal in number to the cavalry division. This type of army, which took an active part in military operations, also had its own uniform. The 19th century author wrote about their clothing: "Soldiers' clothing was different from that of other types of troops and ordinary people. The soldiers were wearing red jacket, red leather trousers and red caps" [49, p. 9].

In the Kokand khanate, the artillery division was officially formed for the first time, during the first reign of Khudayarkhan (1845) [50, p. 9]. It should not be concluded that there was no artillery in the army of the Kokand khanate until Khudayarkhan. In fact, even before Khudayarkhan, the khan's army had artillery. This can be seen in the information of Khorunji Potanin, who was in the Kokand khanate in the 1930s, that there was an artillery in Tashkent. The cannons and artillerymen were usually kept in the fortresses at the frontier points, and they were the basis for the formation of the artillery unit during the first reign of Khudayarkhan.

The sharpshooters division was less than other types of troops in number. It was natural that the soldiers of this division were selected among the other types of army, just as the galabatirs. According to the author of "Tarihi Shohruhiy", the Kokand army consisted of chapavul and iraul divisions, which were engaged in collecting loots and spoils in the occupied territories as a result of the military marches. Their boss was called the 'Kurchibashi'. The place where the weapons of the guards were kept was called a "Kurchikhana"(barn) [51, p. 69].

The khanlikers were engaged in the protection of the khanlikers. During the reign of Amir Temur, the Kurchis were engaged in the protection of arable lands. The khankurchis were engaged in the protection of the lands of the khanate. There were Kurchis during the reign of Amir Temur too and their main duty was to protect the arable lands [52, p. 32].

The army of the Central Asian khanates also had musicians. They challenged the army to battle with various musical instruments, proclaimed victories through music, and served to raise the spirit of the soldiers. For example, there were many musicians in the regular army formed in Bukhara in 1837. In particular, the 700 people strong division of footsoldiers and artillery consisted of 14 drummers, 14 surnay players and 6 karnay players, as well as 2 Turkish drummers and four karnay players [53, p. 213]. Military musicians were organized since the time the permanent army was formed. The 40-member musicians were led by a bandmaster (military orchestra conductor) with the title of yuzbashi. The Kokand army was no exception. Usually in the Kokand khanate, two or three musicians were attached to each group of 20-30 people.

The musical instruments of the military musicians consisted of drums, kettledrums and trumpets. The costumes of the musicians were also different from those of other soldiers. A.P. Fedchenko wrote about one of them: "Among all the soldiers we met, we were amazed by a soldier in a red shirt, and chopon, a black headwear made of sheep skin and a copper plate hanging on the saddle of his horse. Later we found out that he was a cavalry musician" [54, p. 32].

The army music was remarkable for being resonant and noisy. Funds were allocated from the khan's treasury for the clothing of army musicians, their musical instruments and supplies. In one of the archival documents from 1871, Sultan Murodbek ordered Bakhti Muhammad Korboshi to give a drum and a kettledrum to a soldier musician [55, p. 2037]. The military musicians of the Kokand khanate, as in the Bukhara emirate, were paid the same as the soldiers during the marches [56, p. 215]. It can be seen that the attention paid to military musicians and their supply was almost the same as the supply of soldiers.

It is well known that each state declares mobilization to strengthen its military power and to join the army in times of military threats and actions. Military mobilization was carried out in different periods and in different countries on the basis of specific procedures and rules.

In the Kokand khanate all able-bodied men were involved in the military mobilization. The number of soldiers from which area to be mobilized was determined by the government. This rule was also applied to the regular army. It should be noted that any person was drafted into the army, that is, a regular army, as XIX century Russian tourists and officers described [57, p. 61]. In the Kokand khanate, regular military service was inherited, and military service was passed from father to son. If a soldier died in the battle, his weapons were given to his son, and if he did not have a son, then it was given to his close relatives [58, p. 11]. It is true that in some cases, young men who disobeyed their fathers, wandered at night and were caught stealing were also accepted to the army as a punishment. Because military procedures were based on strict discipline, soldiers who violate it were severely punished. In this respect, military service served as a separate school for the above people. Many of these people, who were accepted as a soldier, showed their bravery during the khanate's military operations, including the battles with the Russians.

Soldiers could not leave their places of service without permission. In peacetime, 1/10 of the soldiers were allowed to go to see their families every day [59, p. 115]. A person enlisted in the military did not have the right to withdraw from that list at their willings. Men who were the sole breadwinner of the family and persons with physical disabilities were not included in the military mobilization procedures. This can also be seen by the archival materials from the mid-nineteenth century. Uncle Eshan Ali, the enlistment officer, was asked by an unknown person to release Koldosh

Mahram from military service, that is, to remove him from the military list. The reason was that Koldosh Mahram had many children and his one arm was shorter than the other [60, p. 2019]. In one document from the 1960s, a man named Mulla Sayfiddin Haji requested Mulla Eshmuhammad Akhund, a military enlistment officer to remove his brother Mulla Kozimurod from the list of cavalry division. The reason was his illness and having many children [61, p. 2020]. It is obvious that the military mobilization in the khanate had its own rules, which did not bypass the eastern humanitarian features.

Auxiliary units such as Karakazan (black cauldron) and Karacherik (black cherik), qilquyriq were gathered if necessary, according to the population, the economic power of the region.

It was clear where the number of Karacherik (black cherik) auxiliary units would come from. This in turn made it possible to calculate how many troops the khanate could gather. Auxiliary units involved one or two people from each household. According to Burnashev and Pospelov, who were in Tashkent in 1800, the center had 25,000 apartments, and if one soldier was taken from each house, the number of soldiers would be 25,000 [62, p. 42].

According to the ethnographer R.F. Rassudova, the Bukhara khanate sent 175,000 to 225,000 troops to auxiliary units in the 17th century, 40,000-50,000 in the mid-19th century, 3,000-4,000 from the Fergana Valley in the 17th century, and before Tashkent was part of the Kokand khanate (before 1808) it was possible collect 2,000-3,000 to 30,000 people. In the 19th century, the Kokand Khanate could gather 25,000 troops from Tashkent alone [63, p. 33–34].

From the data of the above sources it can be seen that the number of auxiliary units that could be collected in the khanate was clearly systematized. The mobilization and gathering troops in the khanate was carried out not out of order, but on the basis of certain procedures. This can also be observed in the following case. Mobilization was usually announced in the markets by the announcers. As soon as the mobilization was announced, all had to arrive at the designated place on time. Otherwise, the soldier would be punished besides being left without supplies [64, p. 15].

The governors of the provinces, the beys were responsible for the mobilization of the troops in time, their weapons, clothing, and their presence at the designated place in time as well. Bey was both the administrative and military chief of his territory. In addition to the right to appoint middle and lower-ranking military commanders to the army assembled in his province, Bey also brought the army into battle under the command of the commander-in-chief [66, p. 29]. The number of the troops that the bey should gather was assigned by the central government the khan was running. In some cases, the beys tried to gather as many troops as possible, thereby gaining the khan's attention. Which province had the most troops, the ruler of that province had the most reputation in the palace. This allowed him to intervene in government policy and resolve many issues for his benefit. For example, the governors of Tashkent were always involved in the struggles for the throne in the Kokand khanate. Some governors, on the other hand, tried to reduce the number of regular and mercenary troops in order to reduce the cost of the army, and gain more wealth.

The army was loyal to its bey. Because, all supplies of the soldiers were done by the beys. The good dress and food of the soldiers depended on the wealth and generosity of the provincial governor. If it was on the contrary, the condition of the soldiers got worse too. According to Sattorkhon Abdulgafforov, the governor's house was located in the center of the city, and his house was entered through a large gate, with cannons and constantly armed soldiers on either side of the gate. All the supplies of weapons distributed to the army were kept in the bey's house [67, p. 29]. Bey had three military secretaries; one of them calculated and recorded in a notebook the expenses for the supply of troops. Each bey in the Kazakh and Kyrgyz steppes had their own army and fortress.

By the 50s and 60s of the XIX century, foreign mercenaries from Afghanistan began to serve in the army of the Kokand Khanate. In particular, according to the author of the book “Tarihi Shahruhiy”, in 1864 Jamandar Afghan served as the head of the Kokand artillery. He was aware of European-style procedures in the military [68, p. 81]. During the same period, most of the Russian captives were transferred to the army of the Kokand Khanate. Because most of the captives in the khanate were Kazaks, they were aware of military work. In some cases, captains – the yuzbashi were appointed among them [69, p. 369]. “People of other religions who were taken prisoner were forced

to accept Islam. If a prisoner accepted Islam, he was drafted into the army, if he refused, then he was killed or sold into slavery.” The purpose of recruiting foreign mercenaries and Russian prisoners of war was to train the army to fight in the European style. This situation is in a sense justified. In the battle with the Russians in Chimkent in 1864, the commander of the Kokand artillery, Jamandar Kabuli, mentioned above, ordered the Afghan artillery to spread across the front and open fire. In this way, the Russian army retreated, seeing that it was being fought in the European style [70, p. 127].

The regular recruitment of prisoners of war was also practiced in other khanates of Central Asia. In particular, such a situation existed in the Emirate of Bukhara. In 1837, the Emir of Bukhara Nasrullakhan recruited 800 foreign soldiers and 250 artillerymen for the regular army. The weapons and clothing given to these captives belonged to the commander-in-chief, and the soldiers who served in the regular army did not have their own personal weapons [71, p. 213].

According to the book "Tarihi Shahruhiy", during the reign of Madalikhan the flag of the Kokand khanate was white [72, p. 69]. It was woven of silk, and from the top to the bottom hung hangers. In the army of the Kokand khanate, each of the five hundred divisions had its own flag. Each one hundred division also had its own symbol (coat of arms). The information of the author of the work "Tarihi Shahruhiy" about the flags should not be accepted as very strict and accurate information. Some sources state that different divisions and subdivisions of the Khanate's army had flags of different appearance and different colors. One of the flags looted by the Russians in the city of Turkistan was red, and the flag looted from Akbulak had a shiny gleam [73, p. 86]. In 1842, Madalikhan fought against the Emir of Bukhara Nasrulla with an army of five flags. These flags were blue, white, yellow, red, and one flag was black [74, p. 86].

It should be noted that there was no special educational institution that provided military education and training in the khanate. However, they tried to teach the new soldiers military science in every way. In particular, in the Central Asian khanates, some of the young soldiers were trained in martial arts by skilled and experienced soldiers and they were called “shogirdpesha” (apprentices).

This situation can also be observed in the Kokand khanate. According to the book "Tarihi Shahruhiy", a person named "Normuhammad Kushbegi" brought up 500 “shogirdpeshas” (apprentices) from the children of his close people and relatives [75, p. 75]. It shouldn't be concluded that only young men who had been apprenticed in the khanates had military training. In the Kokand khanate, soldiers underwent military inspections twice a year. These inspections included not only the distribution of uniforms to the soldiers, but also their combat and tactical training, and weapons. The young soldiers mobilized to the regular army of the khanate underwent military training in their chosen areas under the guidance of experienced soldiers until they mastered the secrets of the use of weapons.

Experienced soldiers, the yuzbashi and the onbashi, who were engaged in the conscription of new soldiers, trained them in various traditional ways. In particular, they made extensive use of hunting to master certain military tactical training. During the hunt, the soldiers learned lessons such as siege, mass attack, and orderly retreat. Soldiers who wanted to join the sharpshooters division were given the opportunity to train with rifles, and funds were allocated from the khanate's treasury. The artillerymen, in turn, practiced with the artillery. From time to time, all types of troops also participated in general training together. About the methods of training soldiers in general training in the 70s of the XIX century, the Russian Dm. Dolgorukoy noted: “The artillerymen started the training first. The artillery officer punished a soldier who was slow three times by with a stick. Then the infantry soldiers joined the exercise and attacked and they were supported supported by the cavalry. Such training of the army is much lower than the training of our (Russian army-T.B.) Army” [76, p. 269].

Indeed, military training in the Kokand Khanate was much lower than in the European army. However, the khanate tried to improve the military-tactical skills of the soldiers as much as possible. In order to achieve this goal, they tried to make as much use of traditional military methods as possible.

Soldiers learned how to use firearms, cannons, and how to fight with them. They also conducted many exercises, such as besieging and attacking fortresses, which played an important role

in the Central Asian defense system. A. P. Fedchenko's statement, who witnessed such an exercise, is a clear confirmation of it: "We were surprised by the sound of drums in the evening. Then, we witnessed soldiers training in nearby castles. The training was mainly on the walls of the fortress, and from time to time we saw soldiers running to the walls of the fortress" [77, p. 33].

Soldiers who had undergone special training during the military parade lined up with military commanders. At the beginning of the line there was first artillery, then a group of 20-30 people from each division, and in front of the group there was an officer and next to him there were 2-3 military musicians [78, p. 259].

The division of the army in the Kokand khanate was carried out on the basis of widespread traditions in Central Asia. There preserved ancient tradition of the division of the army in the khanates. The army with many numbers was divided into tuman (consisted of 10000 people), tuman was divided into hazor (1000 people with a flag in the Kokand khanate), hazor was divided into dasta (1000–500 people), dasta was divided into hundreds (with a flag in the Kokand khanate), hundreds was divided into fifties and the fifty was divided into tens.

When the Kokand army set out on a military expedition, each division was accompanied by a group of 5 non-military men. One of their tasks was to take the wounded soldiers out of the battlefield and place them in carts and bury the dead soldiers (whether they were enemies or their own soldiers, if they were Muslims) [79, p. 32].

The representatives of different nationalities mobilized from the Khanate provinces were sent to various fortresses and border points for service after having certain military training. The gathered soldiers served under the command of provincial governors and castle commanders until a state of war broke out. In particular, the permanent army mobilized in and around Tashkent was not involved in military operations in the interior and south of the Kokand Khanate. They were tasked with protecting the northern borders of the khanate and carrying out military operations in the northern territories.

It can be seen that the traditions existing in the army of Amir Temur had a strong influence on the military structure of the army and military tactics in the Central Asian khanates.

During the military actions, the whole army was mobilized and the soldiers were divided into the sides and wings according to the region and nation they were called to mobilization. The wings consisted of right, left and middle – central wings. Such division enabled to use various military tactics in the battles.

This method of division, as mentioned above, was taught to the soldiers by hunting and *ulak* – *kupkari* (a game played on horseback in which players struggle for possession of a headless goat or calf carcass). In the 19th century, this style of division was reflected in the Kupkari race. According to it, the right and left sides competed with each other, and the center was called the middle-mayor, and acted as a judge. In the Kokand khanate, mainly Kipchaks, Kyrgyz and Tajiks competed against the Mings [80, p. 32]. This situation, in turn, was also reflected in the battlefield. The left wing was at a higher level than the right wing in terms of reputation and combat glory. In the Kokand khanate, the central part of the army consisted of representatives of the Uzbek tribe.

The placement on the left and right wings varied during the time of the different khans. During Alimkhan's reign, the left wing was occupied by Tajik soldiers. After the political events that took place in the khanate in the following years, during the reigns of Sheralikhan, Sultan Muradkhan and Khudayarkhan, the Kyrgyz and Kipchaks were on the left wing. Such division also existed in other khanates of Central Asia. For example, in the Bukhara Emirate, Tajiks and Khojas were placed at the center of the army. The left wing was occupied by the Mangits, Kutchis, and Qatagans living in the Zarafshan, Kashkadarya, and Surkhandarya oases, while the right wing was occupied by the Naymans, Qirq Dormons, Karakalpaks, and Turkmens.

The organizational structure of the army of the Khiva khanate was the same as in the Kokand khanate and the Bukhara emirate, consisting of the front avant-garde, the right wing, the center, the left wing and the ambush troops. The central troop usually started the battle, and the fate of the battle depended more on them. After the attack of the avangarde troop, the right and left wing soldiers

Tursunov B. (2023). Yosh olimlar, doktorantlar va tadqiqotchilarning onlayn ilmiy forumi. *Military administration and the structure of the army in the kokand khanate*, 19-34. TATUFF-EPAI.

attacked and blockade the enemy. The troops in the ambush suddenly attacked the enemy and hastened their defeat.

Conclusion. The analyzed historical sources and archival data show that from the time of the establishment of the Kokand Khanate until its occupation by Russia, a permanent army was formed by the efforts of various rulers. Due to the demands of the time, a number of changes took place in the Kokand khanate. The regular army formed and improved during the reigns of the Kokand khans Alimkhan, Umarmkhan, and Madalikhan, was weakened as a result of civil wars during the reign of Sheralikhan. By the time of Mallakhan, Sultan Sayidkhan and Khudayarkhan, reforms were carried out in the existing army, in order to strengthen its material base and increase its tactical readiness. However, not all of the reforms carried out were generally implemented in the army of the khanate. The reforms were applied only to the army stationed in Kokand, the capital of the Kokand Khanate, and the military units in the outlying fortresses of the border cities were excluded from these reforms. In many cases, the growing number of irregular armies relative to the regular army at the height of military actions by various rulers made it difficult to manage the army. Because this unit was aware of military training and certain discipline. At the same time, the periodic development and improvement of the army was not carried out equally during the reign of all the rulers, and as a result, this army could not withstand the threat from the north - the Russian attack.

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FROM THE HISTORY OF TRADE RELATIONS IN THE KHANATE OF KOKAND

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Abstract: *In the the Khanate of Kokand, which was formed in the early XVIII century, economic life gradually took shape. Domestic and foreign trade has developed and the welfare of the population has increased. In turn, the rulers of the khanate also sponsored the development of trade, built markets, Inn on the caravan route, stalls and shops, and controlled the process of trade in the markets. At the end of the XVIII century, the lack of money of the the Khanate of Kokand became an important factor in the development of trade relations.*

In the khanate, with the development of a certain type of handicrafts and separate types of products, separate centers began to detached. Paper, jewelry, saddles and horse-drawn carts, fabrics and handicrafts made of yarn, the silk products of Margilan and Khojand, the mining and livestock products of O'sh and Andijan, the horticultural products and wood products of Namangan, which are in great demand among the population of the Tashkent steppe, Turkestan, the cities of Shymkent, Avliyoota, Sayram were distinguished by livestock and livestock products.

Trade was an integral part of the life of the khanate's population, with markets being set up two or three times a week in large cities, and once a week in large villages and in areas connecting several small villages.

Keywords: *Central Asia, the Khanate of Kokand, handicrafts, silk, cocoon, chilla, skein, silk and semi-silk fabrics, Norbotabi, Umarkhan, Kokand, Tashkent, Namangan, Margilan, O'sh, merchant, tanga.*

As a result of the political turmoil in the Khanate of Bukhara, an independent the Khanate of Kokand was formed in the Fergana Valley in the early XVIII century. The political history of the Khanate of Kokand (1709-1876) can be conditionally divided into four stages:

1. The period of formation of the khanate (1709-50s of the XVIII century). During this period, the the Khanate of Kokand consisted mainly of the Fergana Valley, and the rulers of the khanate were engaged in unifying the country, eliminating internal conflicts, fighting external enemies, and strengthening the country's position.

2. The beginning of the period of development (from the 60s of the XVIII century to the end of this century). It was mainly during the reign of Norbotabi (1763-1798) that the territory of the khanate expanded and began to rise politically and economically. The country also had a small position in Central Asia.

3. Period of development (first half of the XIX century). During the reigns of Alimkhan (1798-1810), Umarkhan (1810-1822), Muhammadalikhan (1822-1842) the territory of the khanate was expanded. The southern regions are connected to the Pamir mountains. The khanate not only strengthened its political position in Central Asia, but also rose significantly economically.

4. The period of decline (50s-70s of the XIX century). During this period, internal conflicts and external wars culminated. The country is in political and economic decline. Struggles for the throne intensified, and the rulers of the khanate were constantly changing.

In fact, Khudoyorkhan came to the throne three times (1845-1858, 1862-1863, 1865-1875) and was forced to resign three times as a result of internal conflicts. The khanate could not defend itself from an external enemy. As a result, in 1842 the Emirate of Bukhara temporarily occupied the Khanate of Kokand, and in 1876, the Russian Empire abolished it.

It is in this system of political realities that the economic life of the country has developed. In the years when the potential of the centralized state is strong, the development of economic life, the development of handicrafts and trade, which constitute it, is clearly visible. New markets, stalls, shops were built, the existing ones were repaired. In turn, the trade process was regulated. The Khanate of Kokand, which had regained its political position from the second half of the XVIII century, had little money and goods-money relations were under control. Trade was an integral part of the khanate's economy and an important source of income for the country. Russian diplomat and ethnographer A.P Khoroshkhin, who was in the khanate in the 70s of the XIX century, spoke about the attitude of the population of the Khanate of Kokand to trade "... 20-30 rub. the sart, who had the money, immediately went into business" (Xoroshxin, 1876, s. 103).

The economic and social situation of the khanate in their time was not so good, as the rulers of Kokand Shahrukhbiy (1709-1721), Abdurahimbiy (1721-1734) and Abdukarimbiy (1734-1750) were engaged in strengthening the political position of the new state, eliminating internal and external enemies. During this period, although traditional trade relations took place, they were chaotic and almost uncontrollable. From the reign of Erdonabiy (1750-1752, 1753-1762) economic life improved slightly and the welfare of the population increased. According to the historian Makhmud Khakim Yayfaniy (1850-1930), everyone lived prosperously during the time of Erdonabiy. The people were grateful for the behavior of the khan (Mahmud Hakim Yayfoniy, QP. 4101, 7 a-varaq).

After the coronation of Norbotabi (1762-1798), a period of relative development of the khanate began. The territory of the the Khanate of Kokand expanded and its position in Central Asia increased. Domestic and foreign trade is developed. The historian Mulla Alim Makhdum describes the rule of Norbotabi as follows: "In the time of him there was no anxiety, restlessness, costliness and famine. The money was introduced during the reign of that khan, and no one could find any other way but to give the grain to the citizens in the warehouse of all the people. In this way, cheapness and generosity were heard in the surrounding provinces, which led to the arrival of large numbers of people in Khokand and the prosperity of Fergana" (Mirzo Olim Mahdum Xoji, 2008, b. 56).

This tariff can also be seen in the work of Makhmud Khakim Yayfaniy. In it: "... everyone was rich and equal, in every house there was a storehouse of grain and there was no choice but to cancel the grain. He would give a sheep for a tanga, and the black money was taken out and introduced by Norbotabi" (Mahmud Hakim Yayfoniy, QP. 4101, 8 b-varaq).

It was noted that strangers would come from all over and gather here. Mulla Niyaz Mukhammad Khokandiy, on the other hand, noted that the improvement of the internal and external situation during the reign of Norbotabi had a positive effect on the development of trade (Mulla Niyoz Muhammad Xo`qandiy, 1885, s. 40 – 45).

During the reigns of Alimkhan (1798-1810), Umarkhan (1810-1822) and Muhammadalikhan (1822-1842) the development of the Khanate of Kokand reached a new stage. The Khanate became one of the largest states in Central Asia. The economy also grew, and the development of domestic and foreign trade had little effect on the well-being of the population.

The urban and rural population exported agricultural and handicraft products to the country's markets, while the mountainous population and nomadic pastoralists exported livestock and livestock products. Local traders went to the remote villages of the khanate and bought the products grown or prepared in that area at low prices, wholesale, and brought them to the big city markets. In turn, there were traders who bought the goods of artisans, and a few who went to the market, the city to the city, the village to the village.

Mukhammad Aziz Margilaniy, a historian of luxury and cheapness in the khanate, "...said that during the time of the Kokand khans, there was little money and cheapness among the people of Fergana. In summer, a cart sells for two and a half to five tangas, a cart sells melons for 3,5 tangas, a basket of apricots for three tangas and 1 tanga, a chaksa (a unit of weight equal to 1/3 pud per chaksa. One pud is

16,3 kg.) the price of rice ranges from one to two tangas, a pud of fresh flour costs more than a tanga, a pistachio costs from fifty paysa (a paysa is given here instead of a small tanga), a pud of pure yellow nuts costs a hundred paysa, some apricots, carrots and onions. You could buy one pul to six pul, you could barely carry it, you could give 40 chaqas for a tanga, you could put that money in your wallet and go to the market and spend it all night, and it would all come back without spending it, and again ... citizens could collect royalties in a short time. He wrote that they were tortured without giving” (Muhammad Aziz Marg’iloniy, 1999, b. 70 – 71).

In the large cities of the khanate there was a market two or three times a week, in smaller towns and large villages, and once in places where several small villages adjacent to each other were connected.

The city of Kokand was the largest economic center of the khanate and played an important role in domestic trade. According to Philip Nazarov, a Russian diplomat and orientalist who was in the khanate from 1813 to 1814, there was a three bazaar which was made of stone, in the center of Kokand, with a market twice a week (Nazarov, 1968, s. 76).

N.I. Potanin, a Russian orientalist who visited Kokand in 1830, pointed out that there were six markets in the capital of khanate (Potanin, 1856, s. 281).

According to the anonymous author, in the 40s of the XIX century, 2 out of 6 markets in Kokand were traded by local traders and 4 by traders from different regions (Obozrenie Kokandskogo xanstva v nineshnem ego sostoyanii, 1849, s. 213).

Some of the Kokand markets were covered with pineapples, which existed in Central Asia, and were also suitable for the rainy season. Kokand market was one of the best markets in Central Asia after the market of Bukhara.

Typical of Central Asian cities, the main market of Kokand is located in the center of the city, at the junction of various streets and is known as the big Bazaar. The Russian orientalist A.L Kun noted that when he came to the capital in 1875, there were about 2000 shops in this market. The main market is divided into separate outlets or small markets, depending on the type of product (Kun, 1875, s. 61 – 62).

The shops in the markets of the cities of Kokand are divided into three types: those belonging to the ruling dynasty and those belonging to various officials, private and Waqf shops. According to archival data, on the eve of the end of the khanate, there were 1911 shops in the markets of Kokand, of which 599 belonged to the ruler, 1312 were private shops (O`zR MDA, I. 276-fond, 1-ro`yxat, 123-ish, 25 – 26-varaq).

According to the Russian orientalist N.Pantusov, during the reign of Khudoyorkhan most of the inns on the caravan route, shops, bathhouses and other commercial buildings in the capital were not taxed. This is because most of them belonged to the khan or were considered the property of the Waqf (Pantusov, *Turkestanskije vedomosti*, 1876, – № 17).

In particular, during this period, 5 out of 10 inns on the caravan route in the city belonged to the khan (Nabiev, 1973, s. 201).

The shops were leased to traders and rent was paid from them in the prescribed manner. In 1874, the khan's treasury received 2131 gold coins from 575 shops in Kokand (Pantusov, *Turkestanskije vedomosti*, 1876. – №13).

The largest trade in the markets of the the Khanate of Kokand took place in the open market areas, while the inns on the caravan route traded in relatively expensive goods, foreign goods and wholesale goods. The Kokand markets were crowded with traders and buyers, with about 600 traders in the main market engaged in small-scale trade alone (Nabiev, 1973, s. 200).

In the middle of the XIX century, when the economic life of the khanate reached a more moderate level, the market in Kokand lasted three days a week on Wednesdays, Thursdays and Sundays from morning to evening. Wednesday is the main market day, and traders from different cities of the khanate and neighboring areas came to the market on this day.

The locals brought handicrafts and agricultural products from the suburbs to the Kokand markets. Also, a variety of products made and grown in different regions of the khanate were sold in Kokand markets. The Kokand market was the main distribution center for goods entering the Fergana Valley from neighboring areas, and traders from different parts of the khanate could be seen in its markets.

Located in Tashkent, one of the largest and richest markets of the the Khanate of Kokand, it was famous not only for its local handicrafts, farming, and horticultural products, but also for its market of goods from Russia and the Kazakh steppes.

In the XVIII and XIX centuries, there were few markets in the Sebzor, Kokcha, Beshyogoch, and Shaykhantakhur districts of Tashkent. The largest market was located in the city center, at the intersection of town's part, and was called Joba (or Jova) market. According to historian Mukhammad Salikh, "...the market stalls continue to the confectionery shop in Chorsu. During the month of Ramadan, there is a market here at night, and people trade and have fun" (O`rinboev, 1983, b. 40).

At the beginning of the XIX century, there were more than 3000 shops in the Joba market (now Chorsu), including shops in the main rows and Inn on the caravan route. In the 60s of the XIX century, the market was 400 sarjins (1 sarjin equals 2,13 meters) and 100 sarjins wide, with 16 inns on the caravan route and 2400 shops. The number of shops in the city reached 4548 (Teterevnikov, 1867, s. 39).

In the 60s of the XIX century, the rent for shops in the Tashkent market was 2 to 4 gold coins a year (Teterevnikov, 1867, s. 39).

The central market in Tashkent was also divided into rows according to the type of product, and in the 60s of the XIX century the number of rows was about 40 (Teterevnikov, 1867, s. 40 – 42).

In Tashkent, as in Kokand, there was a market three times a week on Wednesdays, Thursdays and Sundays. On Sunday, there was a large market, and on that day there were also money exchange shops (O`z RMDA, I. 1-fond, 16-ro`yxat, 876-ish, 8-varaqning orqasi).

Tashkent market is a competitive center of Khojand, Bukhara, Kokand, Margilan silk fabrics. In the middle of the XIX century, 10000 to 15000 camels of cotton, paper, raw silk and silk fabrics, dried fruits were transported from the Fergana Valley to Tashkent via Kokand, 500 camels of dried fruits, 1000 camels of silk and 1000 camels of silk fabrics, the dye of royan a year and so on (Teterevnikov, 1867, s. 48 – 49).

In the first half of the XIX century, more than 10000 camels brought grain, iron, steel, cast iron, copper and copper products, sugar, leather, petroleum and other Russian industrial goods from Tashkent to the Fergana Valley. In the middle of the XIX century, goods worth 4,580,000 rubles were exported from the valley to Tashkent, while goods worth 2,375,000 rubles were exported from Tashkent. During this period, the annual trade turnover of Tashkent and Kokand amounted to 7 million rubles (Maxkamov, 1988, s. 48).

In the early XIX century, Namangan was also famous for its bazaars, which played an important role in trade in handicrafts and horticultural products, as well as in the mountainous Kyrgyz. In the 60s of the XIX century, Khudoyorkhan built a large market of 500 shops in the city. The bulk of the income from this market went to the khan's treasury (O`zR MDA, I. 1-fond, 34-ro`yxat, 122-ish, 9 – 9-varaqning orqasi).

Each shop brought in 5 to 10 tangas a year to the khan's treasury. A.L. Kun wrote in 1875 that there were more than 1000 shops in Namangan (Kun, 1876, s. 64).

The main market of Namangan is divided into rows and small markets, depending on the type of product, as in the major cities of the khanate. While the small market in the city market was held every day of the week, the large market was held several days a week on Saturdays and Sundays from morning to evening, as in the markets of Kokand and Tashkent (Vel'yaminov-Zernov, 1854, s. 43 – 47).

Margilan was distinguished from other markets of the khanate by its market of silk and semi-silk fabrics, which played an important role in foreign trade. With this in mind, the Kokand khans paid great attention to the Margilan market, expanded it and built new rows, shops and Inn on the caravan route.

During the last reign of Khudoyorkhan (1865-1875) there were 2246 shops in Margilan, of which 489 belonged to the ruling dynasty, 686 to Waqf property, and 1071 to private property. Of these shops were sold, 214 sold meat, 401 sold fruits and vegetables, dried fruit, 109 shoes, 46 silk fabrics, 3 cotton, 81 clothes, 86 manufactured goods, 140 perfumery, and 4 silverware (Said Magomed Xudoyar-xan Kokanskiy. *Turkestanskiy sbornik*. Tom 89. s. 332 – 334).

In the Margilan market, small trade operated every day of the week, on Thursdays and Sundays (*Turkestanskiy sbornik*. Tom 26. s. 137).

Andijan was one of the centers of the khanate famous for its small markets. The Russian orientalist P.I Nebolsin described the market in Andijan as follows: “You can see traders from the largest cities of the Andijan khanate, where trade is developed, and in the markets from Bukhara, Khojand, and Kokand” (Nebol’sin, 1855, s. 299).

The market, located in the city center, had more than 1000 shops in the 70s of the XIX century (Kun, 1876, s. 64).

The market is divided into separate stalls and small markets depending on the type of product. In the north of the city there was a horse market, in the south there was a sheep market, in the center there was a shoe market, a horse-drawn carriage, a horse-drawn carriage, a horse-drawn carriage.

In Andijan, Mondays and Sundays were market days, and trade caravans came from different parts of the khanate, as well as from neighboring countries. On other days of the week, small trades took place in the market.

Located on the border of the the Khanate of Kokand and one of the largest trade cities, the O’sh Khanate played an important role in trade relations with Kashgar and the Kyrgyz, and its markets were home to many local and various traders. According to Mir Izzat Ulla, an Indian merchant who visited O’sh in 1812, O’sh was a large city on the Kokand Kashgar road, where goods from different countries were exchanged, and on Tuesday there was a large market in O’sh (*Puteshestvie Mir Izzat Ulli v Kokandskoe xanstvo v 1812 godu*, 1956, s. 48 – 49).

In the middle of the XIX century, there was a large market in the city center with about 1000 shops. On the banks of the Oq Bura River, which runs through the center of the O’sh market, there was a covered market Tim. The two banks of the Ak Bura River are connected by a 900-meter suspension bridge, and market stalls are located on both banks of the river (Galitskiy, Ploskix, 1987, s. 119 – 120).

The O’sh sheep market was one of the most popular livestock markets in the the Khanate of Kokand (Saparaliev, 1999, s. 83).

Khojand, one of the largest cities of the Khanate of Kokand, had 14 market areas for its Thursday and Wednesday markets, where small trade took place. Thursday’s market is located east of downtown, and Wednesday’s southeast. There were 510 stores in the Thursday market and 280 in the Wednesday market (Mirbabaev, 1995, s. 98).

In Khojand, three days a week are Wednesdays, Thursdays and Fridays. In the center of the city, near the intersection of four Street, there was a covered market Tim, which was the center of Khojand market (Tursunov, 1976, s. 61 – 66).

The cities of Turkestan, Shymkent, Avliyoota, Sayram of the Khanate of Kokand are also famous for their small markets. These cities were located on the Russian caravan routes of Central Asia and were known for their Russian cattle and Kazakh livestock as well as livestock products. The Russian orientalist V.V Velyaminov-Zernov reported that in the middle of the XIX century Turkestan had a large market and three inns on the caravan route (Vel’yaminov-Zernov, 1854, s. 45).

To the west of Shymkent is a large market, which before the Russian invasion had 220 shops, and there were such shops in inn on the caravan route. The annual turnover of each store was 1000 to 5000 rubles, and that of the market was 250000-300000 rubles (Teterevnikov, 1867, s. 35).

One of the parts of the market infrastructure formed in the khanate was inn on the caravan route. They had facilities built specifically for the accommodation, storage of goods and animals of traders

from different regions. In addition to the residence of traders in the Inn on the caravan route, there was also the opportunity to trade in its shops. There was also a supply of water in the Inns on the caravan route in the towns and villages along the road. The Inns on the caravan route in the khanate were owned by rulers, private individuals, and religious institutions, such as shops.

There were many inns on the caravan route in Kokand, the capital of the khanate. V.V Velyaminov-Zernov reported that there were 9 inns on the caravan route in Kokand in the middle of the XIX century (Vel'yaminov-Zernov, 1856, s. 111). There were 10 inns on the caravan route in the city of Kokand in the 70s of the XIX century, and one of them- in Zakotasaray there were Russian traders, in another there were cotton traders (Xoroshxin, 1876, s. 40 – 41).

Also, according to an unknown author, there were 15 large and several small inns on the caravan route in Kokand in the 70s of the XIX century (Kokanskoe xanstvo po noveyshim izvestiyam, 1870, s. 34).

Tashkent was one of the cities famous for its inns on the caravan route in the khanate. As the city's role in the economic life of Central Asia grew, so did the number of Inn on the caravan route. According to the Cossack Maksimov, who was in the khanate in the 30s of the XIX century, there were 12 two-storey Urgendjsaroy, Kizilboshsaroy (Persian Palace), Orussaray, Nogaysaray, Kashkarsaray and other inns on the caravan route in Tashkent during this period. Four of these inns on the caravan route were occupied by local merchants, two by Russian merchants, two by Kashgar merchants, and two by Bukhara merchants (Pokazanie sibirskago kazaka Maksimova o Kokanskom vladanii, 1860, s. 117).

S.Ya. Klyucharov, a russian merchant who visited Tashkent in the spring of 1852, indicated that there were 15 inns on the caravan route in the city (Vel'yaminov-Zernov, 1856, s. 37), while the Russian orientalist A.N Teterevnikov wrote and listed 16 inns on the caravan route in the 60s of the XIX century (Teterevnikov, 1867, s. 39).

A.P Khoroshkhin, who was in Tashkent in the 70s of the XIX century, also named 29 inns on the caravan route in the city market (Xoroshxin, 1876, s. 92).

The largest inns on the caravan route in Tashkent are located around the central market, and the Russian orientalist P.I Pashino cites 18 inns on the caravan route in the city and their annual income as follows:

1. Said Azimboy 400,000 rubles, 2. Shirin Khoja Rais 400,000 rubles, 3. Khishtin 280,000 rubles, 4. Isabek (Qadi Isohoja)) 200,000 rubles, 5. Tablecloth 160,000 rubles, 6. Isabek (Qadi Isohoja) 160,000 rubles, 7. Abdurasul 160,000 rubles, 8. Zakat 150,000 rubles, 9. Anonymous 150,000 rubles, 10. Rais 1-120,000 rubles, 11. Rais 2-80,000 rubles, 12. Margilan 80,000 rubles, 13. Mulla Salikh (Solikhbek dodkhokh) 60,000 rubles, 14. Namangan 40,000 rubles, 15. Ismailjon 28,000 rubles, 16. Yolbarskhon 5,000 rubles, 17. Makhramboshi 80,000 rubles, 18. Maiz 32,000 rubles (Pashino, 1868, s. 131).

Russian and Indian in Said Azimboy inn on the caravan route in Tashkent main market, Russian and Guljan in Nurmuhammad Kushbegi, Margilan and Indian in 3 inns on the caravan route named after Beklarbegi, Tashkent and Samarkand in Isabek, Kokand in Makhrambashi, Tashkent and Kokand in Shokhbek, Tashkent and Namangan in Tashkent, Shirin Khoja Rais was stopped by Indians and Mulla Abdul Mutallif by Kazakh traders (Teterevnikov, 1867, s. 44).

In the large market in the center of Namangan, one of the economic centers of the Khanate, 3 nns on the caravan route named – Begi, Degbiz and Mavlavi were active, and the Degbiz inn on the caravan route was two-storied. The Inns on the caravan route of Namangan were built of baked bricks and were rectangular in shape, with a single entrance. There was a special area in the center of the inns on the caravan route and the cargoes of trade caravans were unloaded in this area. Near the walls of the inn on the caravan route were trade shops with awnings, while the awnings protected the shops from the rain, while the second floor of the two-story inns on the caravan route served as a porch. The Mavlavi inn on the caravan route was the largest inn on the caravan route in the city, with about 30 to 40 shops (Mixaylov, 1867, s. 69).

On the eve of the Russian invasion, the largest economic center of the khanate, Margilan, had 8 inns on the caravan route in the central market, 2 of which belonged to Indian merchants. The Margilan inns on the caravan route were beautiful and convenient for traders (Ot Margilana do Osh. Turkestanskie vedomosti. 1882. – № 45).

In the middle of the 60s of the XX century, there were five inns on the caravan route in Khojand (Tursunov, 1991, s. 91). Of these, 4 were considered local and 1 belonged to Indian and Jewish merchants (Kostenko, 1880, s. 448).

In Turkestan, an important transit city of the the Khanate of Kokand, there were four inns on the caravan route in the 60s of the XIX century, two of which were built by the mayor Mirzabi. There were 106 shops in Turkestan inn on the caravan route (Geysns, 1898, s. 292).

On the eve of the invasion of the Russian Empire, there were two inns on the caravan route in Shymkent, one private and one built by the governor of Tashkent Mirzo Akhmad (who was the governor of Tashkent in 1854, 1858 and December, 1864). There were 24 shops in the Mirzo Akhmad inn on the caravan route and 8 shops in the second inn on the caravan route. The inn on the caravan route of Mirza Akhmad was in the shape of a square and there were shops under the walls of the inn on the caravan route (Geysns, 1898, s. 372).

Inns on the caravan route also functioned in the settlements and villages along the important caravan routes that passed through the territory of the Khanate, and they had a positive effect on the development of trade relations.

In addition to living in inn on the caravan route, merchants also had the opportunity to trade. Typically, each of the khanate inns on the caravan route had 12 to 35 shops, and they were mainly engaged in wholesale trade. The merchants rented the inn on the caravan route shops and paid a certain amount of rent. In particular, according to the data of the XIX century, depending on the conditions created in the inns on the caravan route of Kokand and Tashkent and the prestige of the inn on the caravan route, traders paid the manager 3 to 5 tillo a year for the rent of the shop (Geysns, 1898, s. 518).

The inns on the caravan route also had special places for storing camels and horses, and food was provided to them at the expense of the inn on the caravan route. In the middle of the XIX century, merchants paid 5 kopecks for a camel and a horse in the inns on the caravan route of Kokand, Tashkent and Turkestan.

There were a number of opportunities for the rest of the population in the khanate markets. These include teahouses, bathhouses, barbershops and other public facilities. The markets of the khanate of Kokand were also famous for their teahouses. There were dozens of teahouses in Kokand, Tashkent, Namangan, Margilan, Khojand and other major cities of the khanate. In particular, on the eve of the Russian invasion, there were 35 teahouses in the Margilan market alone.

In the markets of the the Khanate of Kokand there were many bathhouses with the necessary conditions. The bathhouses in the khanate markets were famous for their cleanliness and quality of service. The bathhouses had hot and cold water in several small domes, a dressing room, a lounge, a well, a hotel, a kitchen and a bathhouses in the middle. In the middle of the XIX century, there were 6 bathhouses in Kokand and 11 bathhouses in Tashkent (Vel'yaminov-Zernov, 1854, s. 39). On the eve of the Russian invasion, there were 7 bathhouses and 38 barbershops in Margilan (Ot Margilana do Osh. Turkestanskie vedomosti. 1882. – № 45). According to A.P Khoroshkhin, there were 6 bathhouses of Mukhammad Karim khalifa, Normukhammad kushbegi, Mukhammad Saidboy, Borikhoja, Yusufboy in the Chorsu market in Tashkent, and each of them could serve 200 people at a time (Xoroshxin, 1876, s. 92). In the 50s of the XIX century, there were two large bathhouses in the Khojand market, among which was the famous bathhouse named Shamsiboy, built by a merchant named Shamsiboy, which was the largest bathhouse in Khojand (Tursunov, 1976, s. 66 – 67).

The large bazaars of the the Khanate of Kokand were divided into rows, and each row had a few elders. The elder supervised the little row together with his assistant and took 2 tangas or less from each shop in the row. At night, the elder was also responsible for the safety of the rows (Geyns, 1898, s. 521).

The role of state officials - Rais - was great in ensuring the smooth flow of trade in the markets of the Khanate of Kokand and the cleanliness and order. Rais is sometimes called Qadi-rai in khanate cities. The post is open to people of good character, profound knowledge of Sharia law, and great respect among the population. Qadi were sometimes appointed to this position, which is why the Qadi was called the Rais. There was one Rais in each of the major cities of the khanate, and one in several of the small towns and villages. In particular, in Tashkent and Kokand before the Russian invasion there was only one Rais. In addition to overseeing religious ceremonies, the Rais oversaw the trade process in shops, stalls, and markets. It has become a marketplace with more than 10 assistants called Qadi-khalifa on Sundays. The Rais prevented clutter, checked that the scales were working properly and even checked the quality of the items made by the artisans. He also fought against the sale of alcohol. The Rais was also responsible for cleaning the streets, canals and market areas. Dissatisfied with the prices in the market, traders and scales, he heard the complaints of buyers and punished the culprits. The punishment was carried out in two ways, in the first, the accused was beaten with 3 to 39 lashes, and in the second, he was beaten in the market and city streets. The Rais's ruling was severe for ordinary citizens of the khanate, as well as officials and foreigners (Gaffarov Abdul Sattorxon, *Turkestanskije vedomosti*. 1892. – №26).

One of the main occupations of the population of the the Khanate of Kokand was silkworm breeding, and the centers of silkworm breeding were Margilan, Namangan, Kokand, Khojand. The cocoons, raw silk and silk products were exported to the khanate markets and from there to neighboring countries.

Silk produced by the locals is divided into different varieties and the price is set depending on the quality. In October 1871, a pud of chilla, which was considered the highest quality silk in the Kokand market, was sold for 50 to 52 gold coins, tafil for 50 gold coins, Kokand yarn for 28-30 gold coins, and sarnak for 3,5 to 4,5 gold coins (Ot Tashkentского yarmarochного komiteta. *Torgovoe obozrenie*. *Turkestanskije vedomosti*. 1871. – №36).

Most of the products that play an important role in domestic trade are textiles. In this regard, the bulk of the products of active domestic trade was cotton-fabric (karbas). This fabric was mainly used for lining, and on the eve of the Russian invasion, the 18 arshin (arshin length is a unit of measurement with an average value of 71,12 cm.) child of the Tashkent bazaar was sold for 1,5 to 2,5 tangas. In domestic trade, striped cloth made of dyed yarn was also important, and it was used to sew jackets and coats. In the middle of the XIX century, a throne was sold for 10 to 15 kopecks (O`z RMDA, I. 276- fond, 1-ro`yxat, 123-ish, 25 – 26-varaq) in Kokand, 50 to 75 kopecks for an 8-year-old child in Tashkent, and 2 tangas for a pair of children (Adinarov, 1946, s. 52).

Chit is one of the most popular fabrics in the Khanate. In 1874, a child of a high-quality red chit in Kokand was sold for 26 to 1,5 tillos, and a cheetah known as khushvakht (the bright red chit) was sold on credit for 68-78 tangas for a period of 4 to 5 months (*Torgovie zametki*. *Turkestanskije vedomosti*. 1874. – №36).

The Kokand markets were characterized by a variety of silk fabrics and fabrics mixed with yarn and silk. In the middle of the XIX century, “silk”, “duriya”, “bekasam”, “adras”, and “banoras” were sold for 70 to 95 kopecks at the Kokand market (O`z RMDA, I. 276-fond, 1-ro`yxat, 123-ish, 25 – 26-varaq). The atlas was highly valued in the local market, and in the middle of the XIX century in the capital market, a 12 “arshin” atlas was valued at 7 to 8 rubles (O`z RMDA, I. 23- fond, 1-ro`yxat, 1398-ish, 1-varaq). The quality of semi-silk fabrics made in the cities of the valley is mainly sold in Tashkent markets. During this period, in the markets of Tashkent, a one-piece banoras produced in Margilan was valued at 20-25 tangas, bekasam 14-18 tangas, adras 18-20 tangas (Adinarov, 1946, s. 53).

The famous Kokand paper made in the capital was one of the valuable products of the khanate markets. In the 70s of the XX century, traders bought a bundle of 24 sheets of paper at the Kokand objuvoz for 15 kopecks and sold it at the market for 20 to 30 kopecks (Fedchenko, 1878, s. 414). The two existing factories in Kokand produced 150000 sheets of paper worth 2,000 rubles a year (Razvadovskiy, 1916, s. 16). The rulers of the country made a lot of money from the paper mills. In particular, in 1875 Khudoyorkhan earned 418 rubles from paper mills in Kokand (O`zR MDA, I. 276-fond, 1-ro`yxat, 123-ish, 24-varaq).

Carpets, shawls and felt made by nomadic and cattle-breeding population played an important role in the internal trade of the khanate. There were few markets for these products in the cities of the khanate. For example, the carpet market in Andijan and the felt market in Namangan, brought by Karakalpaks and Kyrgyz, were popular. In the 70s of the XIX century, local carpets with a size of 4x2.5 were sold for 30 to 40 rubles at the Kokand market (Golovin, Turkestanskiy sbornik, tom 512, s. 29).

Agricultural products play an important role in domestic trade. Their prices varied depending on the weather, the yield, and the political situation. In particular, in the Kokand market in the 1840s, wheat was sold for 1 ruble, rice for 1 ruble 30 kopecks, corn for 64-65 kopecks, wheat for 1 ruble for 30 kopecks, and rice for 2 rubles for 15 kopecks (Obozrenie Kokandskogo xanstva v nineshnom ego sostoyanii, 1849, s. 186).

Khanate markets are known for their year-round abundance and cheapness of fruit and melon products. In the middle of the XIX century in Kokand one batman (in the XIX century in the Fergana valley 1 botmon was equal to 8-10 puds or 131,044-163,805 kg) grapes 1 tillo, dried apricots 1 tillo, 1 quarter pear 1 ruble 40 kopecks, peach 1 ruble 75 kopecks, walnuts 2 batman 3 tillo, 1 quarter almond 1 ruble 40 kopecks (Vel'yaminov-Zernov, 1856, s. 129), in Namangan 1 botmon grapes 1 tillo, 1 botmon cherry 1.5 tangas, 1 chaksa pear 1 tanga, 2 or 3 botmon apricots sold for 1 tillo (Vel'yaminov-Zernov, 1854, s. 47). In 1856, watermelons were sold for 2 puls, melons for 1 pul, 10 cucumbers for 1 pul, a quarter of dried apricots for 3 puls, and a quarter of grapes for 6 pul (Pokazanie sibirskago kazaka Maksimova o Kokanskom vladanii, 1860, s. 72).

Livestock products had a special place in the khanate's domestic trade relations. In addition to performing the function of transport, livestock made extensive use of their wool, meat, skin, milk and dairy products in the economic life of the population. Due to the fact that the Fergana Valley, which was important for the Namangan Khanate, was located on the Avliyoota cattle road, livestock trade was mainly in the hands of the Namangan people. In late August and September, caravans of thousands of sheep began to enter the markets of Namangan. They were mainly driven from Avliyoota through the Karabura gorge. Through this road, 50000 to 70000 sheep were distributed annually to Namangan and through it to the markets of the Khanate of Kokand (O`zR MDA, I. 1-fond, 34-ro`yxat, 122-ish, 7-varaqning orqa tomoni).

In the middle of the 60s of the XIX century in the market of Kokand the horses were sold for 20-80 tillo, ordinary horses for cargo up to 15 tillo, Kyrgyz horses for 2-6 tillo. The oxen are plowed and fed for their meat, which is more expensive from 4 to 6 gold coins, the average cow to 2,5 gold coins, sheep from 1 ruble to 50 kopecks to 4 rubles, one-humped camel from 8 to 12 tillo, two-humped camel from 5 to 6 tillo, donkey and mule 17 sold for 20 tangas (Kokanskoe xanstvo po noveyshim izvetiyam`, 1870, s. 47).

In the Fergana Valley, timber sales were booming from early June to late autumn. Residents of the villages of Zarkent, Mamay, Nanay, and Navkent, which are part of the Namangan principality, harvested spruce and pine wood from the surrounding mountains and brought it to the markets of Namangan, from where it was distributed throughout the khanate (Nabiev, 1973, s. 201). The principality of Margilan was one of the principal suppliers of timber to the various markets of the khanate, supplying 17000 camels (about 200000 puds) a year, and supplying the country with building materials. On the eve of the invasion of the Russian Empire, the wood of one horse was sold for 1 tanga in the markets of the

Khanate of Kokand. The people of the khanate used sakhsovuls and charcoal as fuel. Large quantities of firewood were brought to the Margilan market from mountainous areas, and 30000 carts of firewood were sold annually (Middendorf, 1882, s. 46, 318, 319). There is also an indoor market for firewood in Margilan, with an annual rent of 53000 tangas (O`zR MDA, I. 1043-fond, 1-ro`yxat, 658-ish . 1-varaq). Coal was brought to the markets of the Khanate of Kokand from Khojand and O`ratepa, and in the middle of the 19th century, 20 to 28 puds of coal were mined overnight near Khojand (Middendorf, 1882, s.339 – 340). Sakhsovul and coal were also brought to the khanate markets by mountain Kyrgyz and Kazakhs. In the 70s of the XIX century, sakhsovuls in a cart was sold for 80 kopecks (Kokan`, 1870, s. 136) and a coal cart for 3 rubles and 50 kopecks at the Kokand market (Vel`yaminov-Zernov, 1856, s. 129).

Precious metals and ores are also imported to the domestic market. In particular, tillo was brought to Namangan markets from Kosonsoy. Silver and lead were mined from the Alatov Mountains and the Ketmontepa Fortress, and from the Lalkhona district near Andijan, and brought to the khanate's markets (Vel`yaminov-Zernov, 1854, s. 30). In the Kokand market, lead powder was sold for 10 tangas (Kokan`, 1870, s.137). 24 km from Mingbulak deposit near Namangan (40 km to the city) and Izboskan near Andijan. Petroleum was extracted from the northern Moylisuv River and from the village of Oyim on the right bank of the Kara-Darya River and exported to local markets (Masson, 1953, s. 64). The locals also used the petroleum in the treatment of various skin diseases (scabies, wounds, etc.). Saltpeter and sulfur were also mined around Khojand, and in the khanate's markets sulfur powder was sold for 9 kopecks (Kokan`, 1870, s. 137). It was brought to the Iron Khanate markets, mainly from Russia, and partly mined by locals around Khojand (Obozrenie Kokandskogo xanstva v nineshnem ego sostoyanii, 1849, s. 183).

The population was less satisfied with the salt produced in Namangan and near O`sh. In the 60s of the XIX century in the khanate markets a pud of salt was sold for 12-14 kopecks. sedimentary salt is cheaper and is obtained from the Sarikol salt mine, which is 8 versts from Kamishkorgan, and its price is estimated at 7 kopecks (Voенно-statisticheskoy sbornik, 1868, s. 137).

The internal and external wars, uprisings, and struggles for the throne in the Khanate of Kokand had little effect on market prices. After Mukhammad Aziz Margilani Sheralikhan (1842-1845) ascended the khanate throne, the merchants "... the Emir of Bukhara took away all our possessions and what we had hidden, let's go around Kokand with a fortress" (Muhammad Aziz Marg`iloniy, O`zRFA SHI. – №11108. 129 a-varaq), as well as the second Khudoyorkhan's struggle for the throne during his reign (1862-1863) "... there was a great increase in prices, the prices in the markets did not stay the same, there was chaos" (Muhammad Aziz Marg`iloniy, 1999, b. 71). During the Kokand uprising of 1876, flour in the capital increased from 65 kopecks to 95 kopecks, rice from 80 kopecks to 1 ruble 20 kopecks, barley from 50 kopecks to 80 kopecks, flour in O`sh, Margilan, Andijan and other cities from 68 kopecks to 1 ruble 10 kopecks, rice from 75 kopecks to 1 ruble 30 kopecks raised (Bobobekov, 1996, b. 112).

After the annexation of Turkestan, Shymkent, Avliyoota, Tashkent, Khojand and other cities of the Khanate of Kokand to Russia, the territory of the khanate became mainly the Fergana Valley. However, the khanate's markets differed from the markets of the cities of the Governor-General of Turkestan by the low prices of products. In the 60s of the XIX century, a pud of silk in Kokand cost 3 rubles 50 kopecks, in O`ratepa 4 rubles 40 kopecks, in Tashkent 5,6 rubles (Yujakov, 1869, s. 110), wheat pudding in Kokand 20-30 kopecks, in Tashkent 50-60 kopecks, barley in Kokand 10-15 kopecks, in Tashkent 40 kopecks, millet was sold for 40 to 50 kopecks in Tashkent, twice as cheap in Kokand, rice for 50 kopecks in Kokand, 1 ruble for 10 kopecks in Tashkent (Kokanskoe xanstvo po noveyshim izvestiyam`, 1870, s. 39), cotton fiber in Tashkent in the 70s of the XIX century for 3 to 7 rubles, and from 50 to 1 ruble in Kokand (Turkestanskije vedomosti. 1870. – №1).

In the markets of the Khanate of Kokand, typical of the Central Asian khanates, there were very few cases of aggravation, and if such a situation occurred, severe penalties were imposed. In particular, Philip Nazarov, who was in the khanate in 1814, wrote that the fingers of a man who weighed a sheep

were cut off and put in a boiling bucket, and the donkey was turned upside down and turned into a bazaar. The one who hit the scales was whipped naked in the market (Nazarov, 1821, s. 60). Such drastic measures have allowed buyers and sellers to move freely in the markets.

Until the 70s of the XX century, the Kokand khans were engaged in maintaining the country's political independence and preventing civil wars. Therefore, the process of trade in domestic trade was carried out through the currency of neighboring khanates, mainly Bukhara tangas and barter. After Norbotabi Kokand ascended the throne, he carried out monetary reform. According to reports, Norbotabi struck copper (fuls) chaqas, and these copper chaqas were popularly known as “black money”. According to historian Niyaz Mukhammad Khokandi, Norbotabi introduced black fuls coins and issued one such tanga (Beysembiev, 1985, s. 67).

After Norbotabi, every khan who ascended the throne of the khanate minted a new currency in his name and picked up the old one. The Kokand khans minted more coins and some of them minted gold coins. In particular, Norbotabi copper chaka, Alimkhan copper chaka and silver coins, Umarkhan first introduced copper and silver coins and in the last years of his reign he again carried out monetary reform and introduced gold coins for the first time in the history of the khanate. During his reign, Muhammadalikhan twice reformed the currency, minting copper, silver and tillo coins. Sheralikhan, Khudoyorkhan and Mallakhon also minted copper, silver and gold coins. Even Shakh Murad, who ruled for several months, minted gold and silver, Sayyid Sultan minted tillo, silver and copper, and Polatkhan and Nasriddinbek minted silver coins.

The capital, Kokand, had the only mint in the country near the Khan's Horde. However, in the early XIX century, there was also a khanate mint in O'sh, where copper tangas were minted (Timkovskiy, 1824, s. 91). The Kokand mint had the capacity to mint 1000 tangas a day (Xoroshxin, 1870, s. 187).

In the Khanate of Kokand serious measures were taken against the production of counterfeit money. According to archival data, Khosilbek Kholnazarov, a citizen of the khanate, was persecuted after it was discovered that he had produced counterfeit tangas. Although he managed to escape from the khanate, special appeals were sent on behalf of the khan to the neighboring khanates to capture him. In the Khanate of Kokand, the mekhtar was in charge of controlling the process of tanga production (O`zR MDA, I. 1-fond, 34-ro`yxat, 144-ish, 5 – 5-varaqning orqasi). The goods of barter in the khanate markets has not lost its importance.

Besides the of currency Kokand, Bukhara, Khiva, Russia and Kashgar were in circulation in the Central Asian markets. This, in turn, led to the formation of a unique monetary system in the country.

Along with the neighboring Bukhara and Khiva khanates, the Khanate of Kokand had direct or indirect trade relations with Russia, the Kazakh steppes, Kashgar, China, Afghanistan, Iran, India, Arab countries, the Ottoman Empire and other countries.

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РАЗВИТИЕ НАУКИ И ТЕХНИКИ И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСТВО

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Аннотация: В этом тезисе рассмотрено мировая тенденция развитие науки и техники. Анализ влияние факторов на человечество.

Ключевые слова: Развитие науки, развитие техники, компьютерные технологии, климат, деградация биосферы.

За последние десятилетия развитие науки и техники набирает феноменальные обороты. Каждый год наука становится все более продвинутой, а техника может сделать намного больше, чем ее предшественники. Но пока что нельзя дать однозначный ответ, какую роль будет в себе нести данная тенденция стремительного развития — положительную или отрицательную. С одной стороны человечество пытается сделать на благо обществу каждое новое открытие, но с другой стороны вскрываются непредвиденные отрицательные события, от которых, в дальнейшем, не так уж легко избавиться.

Развитие науки и техники — это необходимый процесс человеческого общества. Люди используют то, чем наделила их природа — возможностью мыслить и приводить эти мысли в реальность. И у человечества это очень хорошо получается. Нельзя сказать, что все изобретения человечества несут благо обществу, но превосходящее большинство их выполняет свою роль на «отлично». Например, изобретение ядерного оружия удерживает населения от повторения инцидентов первой и второй мировых войн, но с другой стороны, если его используют, пострадает вся планета. Или же атомные электростанции, которые производят дешевую электроэнергию и являются самыми производительными по отношению к другим источникам, но не стоит забывать чернобыльский инцидент. Эта двойственность развития науки и техники останется всегда, будут и плохие и хорошие стороны.

Уже давно произошла замена человеческого труда на машинный на производствах. С одной стороны это положительное событие: люди освободились от тяжелой рутинной работы, и процесс пошел в разы быстрее, что хорошо для предпринимателей, но с другой стороны люди, которые были заменены на машины были вынуждены искать себе новое место работы и естественно доля безработицы увеличилась. И скорее всего, такое будет происходить и дальше. Весь человеческий труд будет постепенно заменяться на технику, которая будет намного производительнее и точнее.

Не стоит забывать о современной проблеме 21 века. Появление компьютеров дало огромный толчок развитию науки и техники: все вычислительные процессы выполняются намного быстрее, теперь не нужно держать огромные кипы бумаг с данными, когда все это может хранить в себе небольшая электронная коробочка, обмениваться информацией стало намного проще. Но с другой стороны, можно наблюдать огромный упадок в социальной составляющей. Люди все чаще предпочитают общение через компьютер и смартфон живому общению, потому что так легче и быстрее. Если компьютерные технологии будут развиваться и дальше, то это может привести к коренным изменениям в социуме. Люди будут полностью изолированы и общаться только через электронные носители, начало этому уже положено и его можно отлично наблюдать в наших повседневных буднях.

Развитие науки и техники позволяет все быстрее производить добычу полезных ископаемых, таких как: нефть, газ, руды и т. д. и в больших количествах. Под вопросом остается, насколько на земле хватит ресурсов, если темпы добычи постоянно растут, а ресурсы никак не восстанавливаются. Сколько осталось времени до полного опустошения Земли от полезных ресурсов, которые необходимы почти во все сферы деятельности

человека? Поэтому ученые озаботились о том, что необходимо найти другое место, которое человечество сможет колонизировать в случае нехватки ресурсов на Земле.

Развитие науки и техники также привело к тому, что чистый воздух превратился в смесь выхлопов и дыма, а также к тому, что возможны глобальные природные катаклизмы такие как: изменение климата, деградация биосферы, дисбаланс воды, водных источников, увеличение отходов, огромного количества не утилизируемого мусора (пластиковые пакеты и бутылки), загрязнение почвы, росту уровня загрязнения различными газами, твердыми частицами и туманообразными соединениями атмосферного воздуха.

По всем этим примерам можно сказать, что развитие науки и техники никогда не будет нести в себе только положительную или только отрицательную роль, это всегда будет смесь исходов. Человечеству необходимо такое развитие, но в то же время, оно является пагубным для определенных сфер деятельности.

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ПРОГРЕСС В ОБЛАСТИ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА: НАУЧНЫЕ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: Данная статья представляет собой обзор основных достижений в области искусственного интеллекта за последние годы. В статье описываются такие технологии, как нейронные сети и машинное обучение, а также роботы с искусственным интеллектом. Рассмотрены примеры практического применения этих технологий в различных областях.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, нейронные сети, машинное обучение, роботы с искусственным интеллектом.

Искусственный интеллект (ИИ) – это сфера компьютерной науки, которая занимается созданием систем и программ, способных выполнять задачи, которые обычно требуют наличия человеческого интеллекта. За последние годы область искусственного интеллекта развивалась стремительно, что привело к значительному прогрессу в научных и технологических достижениях.[2]

Одним из самых интересных достижений в области искусственного интеллекта являются нейронные сети. Нейронные сети - это системы, которые могут "обучаться" и "подстраиваться" под различные задачи. Они были разработаны на основе биологических процессов, происходящих в мозге человека, что позволило сделать их гибкими и универсальными.

Нейронные сети используются во многих областях, включая распознавание речи, обработку изображений и машинный перевод. Они позволяют компьютерам выполнять сложные задачи, которые ранее были доступны только людям. Например, с помощью нейронных сетей можно обучить компьютер распознавать образы на фотографиях или даже создавать оригинальные картины.

Другим важным достижением в области искусственного интеллекта является машинное обучение. Машинное обучение - это подход, который позволяет компьютерам "обучаться" на основе предоставленных данных и знаний. Как только компьютер обучается, он может использовать эти знания для решения задач.

Машинное обучение используется во многих областях, включая финансы, медицину и автомобильную промышленность. Он позволяет компьютерам быстро анализировать огромные объемы данных и выделять из них наиболее важную информацию.[4]

Еще одной интересной областью, которая развивается вместе с искусственным интеллектом, являются роботы с искусственным интеллектом. Эти роботы могут использоваться в различных областях, от производства до медицины и сельского хозяйства.

Роботы с искусственным интеллектом обладают большим потенциалом, так как они могут выполнять задачи, которые раньше могли выполнить только люди. Например, они могут быть использованы для производства товаров на фабриках, что повышает производительность и снижает затраты. Роботы могут также использоваться в медицине для выполнения сложных операций, которые требуют высокой точности и стабильности.[1]

Одним из самых известных примеров роботов с искусственным интеллектом являются роботы-ассистенты. Они могут помочь людям в ежедневных задачах, например, в готовке еды, уборке дома или заботе о больных и пожилых людях.

М.Хасанова & Н.Авазова (2023). Yosh olimlar, doktorantlar va tadqiqotchilarning onlayn ilmiy forumi. *Прогресс в области искусственного интеллекта: научные и технологические достижения*, 50-51. TATUFF-EPAI.

Некоторые компании уже начали использовать роботов-помощников для упаковки и доставки товаров. Такие роботы могут сортировать и упаковывать товары, а затем доставлять их клиентам. Это сокращает время и затраты на доставку, что повышает удовлетворенность клиентов и делает бизнес более эффективным.[3]

В целом, роботы с искусственным интеллектом представляют огромный потенциал для автоматизации различных задач и повышения производительности. Однако, с развитием этой области возникают и новые проблемы, связанные с безопасностью и этическими вопросами. Например, в какой момент робот перестает быть инструментом и начинает быть субъектом? Как защитить людей от неправильного использования роботов?

Несмотря на значительный прогресс в области искусственного интеллекта, все еще существуют ограничения и вызовы, которые нужно решать в будущем. Одним из главных вызовов является этика использования искусственного интеллекта, включая проблемы безопасности и конфиденциальности данных. Также необходимо улучшать прозрачность и объяснимость процессов принятия решений, особенно при использовании искусственного интеллекта в критических сферах, таких как медицина и авиация.

Однако, несмотря на вызовы и ограничения, прогресс в области искусственного интеллекта продолжает удивлять и радовать своими достижениями. Большой вклад в этом вносят научные и технологические компании, которые инвестируют в исследования и разработки, а также университеты и лаборатории, которые проводят фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в этой области.

Интересно, что раньше искусственный интеллект рассматривался скорее как наука о компьютерах, чем наука о человеке. Однако сегодня технологии искусственного интеллекта все больше становятся частью нашей жизни, и важно помнить о том, что они должны быть разработаны с учетом потребностей и интересов людей.

В заключение можно сказать, что прогресс в области искусственного интеллекта уже сегодня влияет на нашу жизнь и будет продолжать это делать в будущем. Важно, чтобы разработки в этой области были этичными и соответствовали интересам людей, и чтобы мы могли использовать их для создания лучшего и более продуктивного мира.

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